

STATE OF THE ART ANALYSIS

Deliverable 2.4 – M12

NeuroStimSpinal Identifier	829060_D02.4_State of the art
Submission date	29 February 2020
Actual date of submission	29 February 2020
Responsible partner	1 – UNIVERSITY OF AVEIRO
Internal reviewer	1- UNIVERSITY OF AVEIRO
Written by	Luis Nero Alves (UAVR) Patrícia Martins (UAVR= Bruno Figueiredo ('Graphenest')
Contributed by	Goran Bijelic (Tecnalia)
Confidentiality	Public

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Status of document / Reason of change (responsible person)
1	29 February 2020	First draft (UAVR)
2		

Contents

1.	INTRODUCTION.....	4
2.	BACKGROUND CONCEPTS	6
2.1.	The Memristor.....	6
2.1.1.	Dynamic Route Maps	8
2.2.	The Hodgkinson-Huxley Axon Model	8
2.2.2.	Sodium Channel Dynamics	11
2.3.	Electrode Kinetics.....	12
2.3.1.	Cyclic voltammetry.....	13
2.3.2.	Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy.....	14
3.	NEURAL STIMULATION CONCEPTUAL SCHEMES.....	17
3.1.	Electrical Stimulation.....	17
3.2.	Optical Stimulation.....	19
3.3.	Chemical Stimulation.....	20
4.	ELECTRICAL STIMULATION SPECIFICATION'S	22
4.1.	State-of-the-art Assessment	22
4.2.	In-Vitro Stimulation System Specification.....	24
4.3.	In-Vivo Stimulation System Specification.....	25
5.	ELECTRODE'S MATERIALS AND GEOMETRIES	26
5.1.	METAL Electrodes.....	28
5.2.	Platinum Electrodes	28
5.3.	Gold Electrodes	29
5.4.	ORGANIC Electrodes.....	29
5.4.1.	Conductive polymers-based electrodes.....	29
5.4.2.	Polypyrrole	30
5.4.3.	PEDOT.....	30
5.4.4.	PANI	30
5.5.	Carbon-based electrodes	31
5.5.1.	CNT	31
5.5.2.	Graphene.....	32
5.6.	Hybrid electrodes	34
5.6.1.	PEDOT–CNT	34
5.6.2.	Polypyrrole – graphene	34
5.6.3.	Polyaniline-graphene.....	35

5.6.4.	Polycaprolactone fumarate-Polypyrrole	35
5.6.5.	Polypyrrole-polydopamine	35
6.	FINAL REMARKS.....	44
7.	REFERENCES.....	45

List of figures

Figure 1 - Schematic representation of the methodologies steps projected to achieve SCI repair	4
Figure 2 - Example of the fingerprints of an ideal current-controlled memristor, showing the pinched hysteresis loops when driven by a sinusoidal current and the limiting frequency behavior.....	6
Figure 3 - Memristor definitions (current controlled versions, voltage controlled).....	7
Figure 4 - Dynamic route map of a hypothetical memristor.....	7
Figure 5 - Details of the Hodgkinson-Huxley experiment: a) schematic showing the neuron and axon; b) the HH model, comprising dissipative couplings and HH cells; c) details of the experimental set-up used to measure the current through the axon.....	9
Figure 6 - HH cell equivalent circuit, depicting the two memristors associated to the sodium and potassium ionic channels.	9
Figure 7 - Fingerprints of the potassium channel memristor: pinched hysteresis loops and admittance mapping for different frequencies, under sinusoidal excitation.	10
Figure 8 - Illustration of the LTD (blue curves) and LTP (red curves) process with the Potassium channel memristor: In the LTD process, the admittance decreases making the current passing through weaker (depressed). In the LTP process, the admittance of increases gradually, making the through stronger (potentiated).....	11
Figure 9 - Fingerprints of the potassium channel memristor: pinched hysteresis loops and admittance mapping for different frequencies, under sinusoidal excitation.	12
Figure 10 - Simulation results of applied voltage and simulated current during a CV analysis	13
Figure 11 Bode and Nyquist plots of frequency sweep for Randles circuit	15
Figure 12 Randles circuit reconstruction under the presence of random perturbations.	15
Figure 13 Absolute error trends for different number of samples.	16
Figure 14 - Conceptual circuits for voltage (a) and current stimulation (b).....	18
Figure 15 - Different types of PNI according to their sensitivity and invasiveness. (Kim and Romero-Ortega, 2012).....	27

List of tables

Table 1 - Summary of electrode characteristics used for direct coupling electrical stimulation.....	19
Table 2 - Summary of multifunctional probes for optical stimulation.....	20
Table 3 - Summary of multifunctional chemical stimulation probes.	21
Table 4 - Different stimulation techniques based on Blint et al., 2013. ESC, embryonic stem cell; MSC, mesenchymal stem cell; ROS, reactive oxygen species; ECM, extracellular matrix; TGF transforming growth factor; ALP, alkaline phosphatase; VEGF, vascular endothelial growth factor.....	24
Table 5 - In-vitro and in-vivo system specification summary.....	24
Table 6 - Summary of systems used for electrical stimulation	36

1. INTRODUCTION

The design of implantable medical devices is usually a complex and multidisciplinary task. In what concern electronic systems, considerations such as size and form factor, power consumption, energy harvesting means, stable and continuous operation, biocompatibility and security are of paramount importance. Neural stimulation devices are not an exception.

Figure 1 - Schematic representation of the methodologies steps projected to achieve SCI repair

Therapies of spinal cord injury patients target the important objective to restore neural paths that have been compromised. Project NeuroStimSpinal proposes a radical approach to this problem comprising an innovative stimulus responsive cell-laden biomaterial able to repair the injured nervous tissue. The proposed innovative biomaterial characteristic is a scaffold for implantation in the traumatic injury point composed of graphene-based materials in combination with human adipose derived decellularized tissue, coupled with a wireless electrical stimulation device to promote the growth and reconnection of the ruptured nerves.

The electrical stimulation unit will have to interact with a system comprising the scaffold filled with the biomaterial where the nervous tissues will grow. These interactions is accomplished with the addition of electrodes. In conjunction, the electrodes, the scaffold and the nervous tissues, present a complex and non-linear electrical impedance. Application of voltage (or current) pulses raise quite naturally constraints on the maximum compliance currents (or voltages) that the unit must handle.

The shape and pattern of the stimulation signals is also of concern. It has been established in many studies, that electrical stimulation favors the growth of the nervous tissues. However, there seems to be little consensus on the shape and pattern of the applied signals. The qualitative understanding of how neural cells react to electrical signals may disclose important clues. In this sense, what seems to be of higher importance is not the shape of the signals but the charge these signals transfer into the system.

Another challenge is linked to the material of the electrodes. Here it is not only important to ensure the biocompatibility, as the electrodes directly interact with cells (the stimulation device will require dedicated encapsulation to ensure biocompatibility). Different materials have been investigated for this purpose. Furthermore, different materials promote different electrical behavior (impedance).

This deliverable starts by presenting models for the impedance of biological synapses and electrode kinetics. The qualitative understanding of these models reveals some clues which are of mainstream usage in stimulation devices. Section 3 describes the concept of neural stimulation and possible approaches to the problem. Section 4 focuses on electrical stimulation, the state-of-the-art and specifications for the system to be developed. Section 5 discusses the state-of-the-art of materials for electrodes. Section 6 concludes the deliverable.

Figure 2 - Example of the fingerprints of an ideal current-controlled memristor, showing the pinched hysteresis loops when driven by a sinusoidal current and the limiting frequency behavior.

2. BACKGROUND CONCEPTS

This section presents and discusses models for the impedance of neural cells and electrode kinetics. These models provide a qualitative means to investigate the behavior of the impedance of the real system. The section begins by introducing the memristor, a device theoretically predicted in 1971 by Leon Chua (Chua, 1971), which plays a key role in the understanding of how biological brains work.

2.1. The Memristor

The memristor was proposed in 1971 by Leon Chua as an electrical element linking the relation between charge and flux linkage (Chua, 1971). Electrical circuit theory had, by that time, a set of elements that was thought to be complete. These are the resistor, the inductor and the capacitor. Each of these elements link two electrical variables in their definition: voltage and current in a resistor, voltage and charge in a capacitor, current and flux in an inductor. Other two relations come from Maxwell equations, and link current and charge, and voltage and flux. To be mathematically consistent, these set should include the missing relation between charge and flux. What Chua realized is that an element building upon a flux-charge relation gives rise to a resistor. Moreover, if this relation is non-linear, it gives rise to a resistor with memory. The memristor found in those initial year great opposition and disbelief, in part due to the fact, that there was no element showing the properties highlighted by Chua. These properties stated for the first time in 1971 paper (Chua, 1971) are still valid today and define what became known as the fingerprints of the memristor (see figure 2). Very shortly, the fingerprints of the memristor are: i) the voltage-current relation, exhibits hysteresis loops pinched at the origin when the device is stimulated by a periodical and symmetric signal; ii) the area of the hysteresis decrease with frequency; and iii) for high frequencies the pinched hysteresis loops degenerate in a single valued relation (Adhikari et al., 2013). In another paper (Chua and Kang, 1976), the authors extended the definition of the memristor to a class of devices which became known as

Figure 3 - Memristor definitions (current controlled versions, voltage controlled)

Figure 4 - Dynamic route map of a hypothetical memristor.

memristive devices. One of the examples offered as memristive device was the model of the axon of a giant squid, proposed by Hodgkinson and Huxley (Hodgkin and Huxley, 1952). Since then, not much interest was raised by the memristor, a situation that regrettably sustained till 2008, when a paper by Hewlett-Packard researchers established a link between resistive switching devices and the memristor (Strukov et al., 2008). Resistive switching devices are of high relevance for the electronics industry, in particular for high density non-volatile memory chips and neuromorphic computing platforms. This was the beginning of a new era for memristors, with a high number of research groups investing both in theory and device fabrication.

The definition of the memristor suffered several modifications and generalizations (Chua, 2015, 2014). Figure 3 depicts an overview of different definitions, starting with the ideal definition for 1971, and progressing to higher complexity of the extended memristor. In the most general form, the extended memristor has a set of defining equations, given by,

$$v = M(x, i)i \quad (2.1)$$

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = f(x, i) \quad (2.2)$$

Equation 2.1 is the input-output mapping function, which is general may depend on the input, in the present case, current, i , and state, x . For simplicity sake, x is assumed a single variable, but in general

in can be a multi-valued vector of state variables. The only restriction applied is that $M(x,0)$ must have a finite value. The second equation (2.2) is the state equation, specifying how the state evolves in time. The state equation plays a key role in the analysis of the behavior of the memristor. An important aspect is the fact that this is a differential equation, which implies that the state depends on the previous history of the stimulus and state.

2.1.1. Dynamic Route Maps

Dynamic route maps (DRM) are graphical tools that allow to have a good insight on the behavior of differential equations. In the case of a memristor, DRMs are of paramount importance as they reveal important information on how the state evolves. The DRM plot is a family of curves for the state equation, the vertical scale shows how the time derivative of the state changes, while the horizontal axis shows the state values. The multiple curves on the plot, are the representation of the graphs of $f(x,I)$ when I assumes fixed values.

Figure 4 provides an example of a DRM plot of a hypothetical current controlled memristor. As the plot shows, there are two distinct regions in the plot: the upper part, where dx/dt is positive and the lower part, where dx/dt is negative. When dx/dt is positive, means that the state will increase, that is, it moves to the right of the plot. When dx/dt is negative, the state decreases, moving to the left of the plot. Also, depending on the applied current, the state will move along a specific curve, say, when $I=I_3$, the state moves on the top red curve. The amplitude of dx/dt , tells us how fast the state moves. So, when $I=I_3$, the state evolves faster from $x=x_1$ to $x=x_2$ than when $I=I_1$, for the same amount of time Δt . In this sense, dx/dt is a measure of the velocity of the state update. This is a very important and remarkable characteristic of memristors, shared with biological synapses. In that we can trade stimulus amplitude for stimulus duration to reach the same effect (Chua, 2018).

Another interesting feature revealed by the DRM lies on the curve for $I=0$, known as power-off-plot (POP). It says how the state evolves in the absence of stimulus. When the POP coincides with the horizontal axis, the state freezes, since $dx/dt=0$, there is no evolution. Memristors with such characteristics are universal memories, that is, are capable of non-volatile memory retention properties and are passive (meaning, memory retention does not depend on an external power source). This is also shared by biological synapses, which behave as passive devices and have information storing characteristics (Chua, 2018).

Another important aspect that can be easily understood using the DRM, is the concepts of long-term potentiation (LTP) and long-term depression (LTD). These processes explain how biological synapses learn from experience. The current reasoning is as follows, synapses that are frequently stimulated (used) see their strength improving, or potentiated (LTP). While, synapses that are seldom stimulated, lose their significance, or get depressed (LTD). It is remarkable that memristors, devices theoretically predicted in the frame of circuit theory, exhibit a similar behavior. In fact, several experiments have repeatably demonstrated how memristors, see (Chua, 2018, 2015, 2014) for examples. To understand the dynamics of LTP and LTD in memristors, assume that $M(x,i)$ is some monotonic increasing function of x . Applying a sequence of positive stimuli (positive amplitudes) to the memristors lead to the increase of the state variable (x moves to the right), this means that $M(x,i)$ will increase, that is, it is potentiated. On the contrary, applying a sequence of negative stimuli (negative amplitudes), leads the state to decrease, leading $M(x,i)$ to decrease, or being depressed.

2.2. The Hodgkinson-Huxley Axon Model

This section justifies the need for the introduction of the memristor and its interesting features. The reason to bring this discussion is simply explained with the Hodgkinson-Huxley model for the Axon. In

Figure 5 - Details of the Hodgkin-Huxley experiment: a) schematic showing the neuron and axon; b) the HH model, comprising dissipative couplings and HH cells; c) details of the experimental set-up used to measure the current through the axon.

Figure 6 - HH cell equivalent circuit, depicting the two memristors associated to the sodium and potassium ionic channels.

1952, Hodgkinson and Huxley introduce the electrical model of the axon of the giant squid *Loligo Pialii* (Hodgkin and Huxley, 1952). This model has stood the test of time and prevailed as a reference model in the fields of neurophysiology and brain research. The giant squid is endowed with very large axons, reaching 1mm diameter for large specimens, which make the experiments and tissue extraction simpler. The HH circuit model, has it became known, describes the current conduction as a process composed of two ionic currents carried by potassium and sodium ions. In its original form, the model included time varying resistances associated to these processes. These seems unconventional from the circuit theoretic point of view. A correct description states that these resistances should dependent on the applied voltage and not directly on time. The original paper by Hogkinson and Huxley, raised concerns due to the prediction of effects that were not plausible for biological nerves. The model predicted the presence of signal rectification, something which was taught to be possible in semiconductors and valves. A second effect was that the current exhibited inductive behaviors, though none of these could be directly traced in brains. These concerns were only clarified recently in (Chua et al., 2012a).

The explanation for this inconsistency raised due to the memristive nature of the model. In the more recent formulation introduced by Chua, the potassium and sodium channels are described by a state dependent Ohm's law similar to what is found in extended memristors. The potassium channel is a 1st order memristor, with one state variable, while the sodium channel is a 2nd order memristor with two

Figure 7 - Fingerprints of the potassium channel memristor: pinched hysteresis loops and admittance mapping for different frequencies, under sinusoidal excitation.

state variables (Chua et al., 2012a). Figure 5 details the Hodgkinson-Huxley model. The model has distributed nature, with several HH cells connected by dissipative couplings. All elements in the HH cells are thus expressed as densities. Each HH cell, is described according to the circuit of figure 6. The model comprises 7 elements: C_M models capacitive effects, memristor G_{Na} and voltage source E_{Na} describe the sodium channel, memristor G_K and voltage source E_K describe the potassium channel, while G_L and E_L account for dissipative effects. The HH model is a non-linear with high complexity, which prevents its adoption for large networks of neurons. For that matter, models with reduced complexity, such as the LIF model (Leak-Integrate-and-Fire) are commonly used. The HH model allows deeper investigation on the effects of single synapses, such as the emergence of edge of chaos (Chua et al., 2012b, 2012a).

2.2.1. Potassium Channel Dynamics

The dynamics of the potassium channel current conduction are adequately represented by a 1st order extended memristor, described by the following equations (Sah et al., 2014),

$$i_K = G_K(n)v_K \quad (2.3)$$

$$\frac{dn}{dt} = \left(\frac{0.01(v_K + E_K + 10)}{e^{\frac{v_K + E_K + 10}{10}} - 1} \right) (1 - n) - \left(0.125e^{\frac{v_K + E_K}{80}} \right) n \quad (2.4)$$

Where $G_K(n) = \overline{g_K}n^4$ is the voltage-current mapping function. Simulation of these equations reveals the memristive nature of the model. Figure 7 depicts an illustration of the fingerprints of the potassium channel memristor, when driven by a sinusoidal voltage of different frequencies. Figure 7 also, shows the double valued admittance mapping $G_K(n)$. Figure 8 provides an illustration of the LTP and LTD process in the potassium channel. For this study, the stimulus consisted of a sequence of positive

Figure 8 - Illustration of the LTD (blue curves) and LTP (red curves) process with the Potassium channel memristor: In the LTD process, the admittance decreases making the current passing through weaker (depressed). In the LTP process, the admittance of increases gradually, making the through stronger (potentiated).

(negative) pulses for the LTD (LTP) process. The current through the potassium channel is highly asymmetrical (in both amplitude and shape), due to the dynamics of the channel. In the LTD case, the current at each pulse decreases in amplitude, leading to a decreasing admittance, resulting in the depression of the channel. For the LTP case, the current at each pulse increases in amplitude, leading to an increase in the admittance. This favors the conductivity of channel, that is, potentiates the channel.

2.2.2. Sodium Channel Dynamics

The dynamics of the potassium channel current conduction are adequately represented by a 2nd order extended memristor, described by the following equations (Sah et al., 2014),

$$i_{Na} = G_{Na}(m, h)v_{Na} \quad (2.5)$$

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = \left(\frac{0.1(v_{Na} - E_{Na} + 25)}{e^{\frac{v_{Na} + E_{Na} + 25}{10}} - 1} \right) (1 - m) - \left(4e^{\frac{v_{Na} - E_{Na}}{18}} \right) m \quad (2.6)$$

$$\frac{dh}{dt} = \left(0.07e^{\frac{v_{Na} - E_{Na}}{20}} \right) (1 - h) - \left(\frac{1}{e^{\frac{v_{Na} - E_{Na} + 30}{10}} + 1} \right) h \quad (2.7)$$

Where $G_{Na}(m, h) = \bar{g}_{Na}m^3h$ is the voltage-current mapping function. Simulation of these equations reveals the memristive nature of the model. Figure 9 depicts an illustration of the fingerprints of the potassium channel memristor, when driven by a sinusoidal voltage of different frequencies. Figure 9 also, shows the double valued admittance mapping $G_{Na}(m, h)$.

Figure 9 - Fingerprints of the potassium channel memristor: pinched hysteresis loops and admittance mapping for different frequencies, under sinusoidal excitation.

2.3. Electrode Kinetics

Electrochemistry measures are widely used to understand the interaction electrode-cell and consequently the solution characteristics. Due to this, the electrode characteristics and the essential physical laws must be considered in a first place since the interactions electrode-electrolyte must be well known in order to understand the system's characteristics when some sort of variation on the standard conditions occur (Olivieri et al., 2006).

The electrodes play an important role in electrochemistry analysis. Furthermore, their interaction with the cell can determine many of the visible phenomenon and also helping improving results in a simpler and better way according to the configuration, 2, 3 or 4 probes.

There are two different kinds of current in electrochemical cells, faradaic and capacitive currents, also known as non-faradaic (Scholz, 2015):

- The faradaic currents are responsible for the mass transfer and can be related with diffusion, migration or convection transport mechanisms that should be considered according to the cell characteristics.
- The non-faradaic currents are the result of the polarized molecules accumulation near the electrodes' surface, creating a capacitive layer also known as electrochemical double layer (EDL).

The Butler-Volmer (equation 2.8) equation and Fick's laws (equations 2.9 and 2.10) are especially important when the goal is to understand this electrochemical phenomenon (Bard and Faulkner, 2001). The Butler-Volmer equation describes the electrode kinetics in terms of the applied potential and the chemical species concentrations. The chemical species are dependent on the electrode material composition and the electrolyte. Fick's Laws for diffusion allow to determine how the concentrations evolve in in time and space. Here for simplicity sake, we assume a simple one-dimensional model. It is important to understand that Fick's laws apply only for the case where migration and convection transport mechanisms are absent. When these transport mechanisms are

Figure 10 - Simulation results of applied voltage and simulated current during a CV analysis

important (migration due to the strength of the applied potential, or convection due to stirred solutions), equations 2.9 and 2.10 must be replaced by the more general

$$I = F A k^0 (c_0(0, t) e^{-\alpha \frac{F}{RT} (E - E^{0'})} - c_r(0, t) e^{(1-\alpha) \frac{F}{RT} (E - E^{0'})}) \quad (2.8)$$

$$j_i(x, t) = -D_i \frac{\partial c_i(x, t)}{\partial x} \quad (2.9)$$

$$\frac{\partial c_i(x, t)}{\partial x} = -D_i \frac{\partial^2 c_i(x, t)}{\partial x^2} \quad (2.10)$$

Note that I is the current flowing through the cell, j_i is the electrode current density associated to the chemical species i , F is the Faraday constant, T is the absolute temperature, R is the universal gas constant, E is the electrode potential, A is the area of the electrode, c_i is the concentration of the i specie and α is the charge transfer coefficient. x and t are the position and time, respectively.

$${}_0^C D_t^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{c_i}{c_i^*} = \pm \frac{I}{F A \sqrt{D_i c_i^*}} \quad (2.11)$$

$${}_0^C D_t^\alpha f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n - \alpha)} \int_\alpha^t \frac{f^{(n)}(\tau)}{(t - \tau)^{\alpha+1-n}} d\tau \quad (2.12)$$

Equation 2.11 shows the form of the general solution of the Fick's equations for infinite planar electrodes immersed in non-stirred solutions, where α is the fractional order and Γ is a convolution integral: $\Gamma(z) = \int_0^\infty x^{z-1} e^{-x} dx$ para $\Re(z) > 0$. Solutions for cylindrical electrodes are similar in form, with differences due to the geometry of the electrodes. This solution comes in the form of a fractional differential equation, where the differential operator, is defined in Caputo sense according equation 2.12. It is interesting to see that this form shares in common the differential nature of the state equations in a memristor (Martins, 2019).

2.3.1. Cyclic voltammetry

Cyclic voltammetry is an electrochemical method used to experimentally characterized cells, it can be directly simulated using Butler-Volmer equation (2.8) and the solution of the Fick's laws (2.9 and 2.10) for the specific conditions of the interaction. The electrons are ejected on one of the electrode based

on a triangle waveform signal (figure 10) and the current that flows through the cell is measured causing a duck shape hysteresis loop as shown in figure 10. There are many variables that can provide different “duck shape” characteristics: the redox pair, the other compounds in the solution, the sweep characteristics, environmental variables and the set-up physical characteristics (electrodes’ material, distance between them, etc.) (Martins, 2019).

From the CV cycle, it is possible to infer several features of the electrode-electrolyte reaction, such as the cathodic and anodic currents. Those currents are reached when all the substance at the surface is reduced or oxidized, respectively, and they are represented as the maximum and minimum value of the current during the CV voltage sweep. These currents are especially important because when the composition of the solution varies, also these peaks can change and provide information about these compounds and the solution state (Martins, 2019).

2.3.2. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy, EIS, is a method usually applied for the sensing of electrochemical sensors and small signal characterization of electrode reaction. This kind of sensing systems is one of the most complex ones as it entails a small signal excitation and frequency sweeping protocols. Being a small signal method, the extracted characterization of the cell is also a small signal equivalent circuit, composed by linear elements. This small signal equivalent circuit is commonly referred in the literature as Randles circuit (Bard and Faulkner, 2001). Figure 11 depicts the typical impedance chart and the associated Randles circuit when excited with a sequence of sinusoidal signals with varying frequencies. The Randles circuit comprises four elements: i) the limiting resistance R_s , which corresponds to the resistance of the sensor at infinite frequency; ii) the transfer resistance R_{ct} , usually representing the sensitivity of the transducer to some particular chemical species; iii) the C_{dl} , representing the non-Faradaic response of the transducer, usually modelled as a capacitive double layer accounting for the interface between the transducer and the aqueous environment; iv) and the Warburg element Z_w , which accounts for the low frequency response of the transducer, typically exhibiting a 45° degrees inclination ($Z_w = A_\omega / \sqrt{j\omega}$).

Experimental EIS uses dedicated laboratory equipment such as VersaSTAT 3 from AMETEK, Inc. These equipment includes a potentiostat (the cell interfacing circuit), a DDS system (direct digital synthesizer, responsible for the generation of the excitation signals) and a vector analyzer (embedding a FFT engine (fast Fourier transform) responsible for the signal analyzes in the frequency domain). The potentiostat is highly sensitive instrumentation amplifying chain, design to ensure stable operation and negligible perturbation on the reference electrode. In the frequency domain, the impedance values are represented by default by real and imaginary parts. The Randles circuit extraction step involves non-linear optimization methods, such as non-linear least squares based on Levenberg-Marquard or trust-region-reflective algorithms. This procedure outputs the set of circuit parameters $P=\{R_s, R_{ct}, C_{dl}, Z_w\}$ that best match the set of impedance values taken by the EIS system. Mathematically the problem specification can be cast as:

$$P = \min_P \sum_k (y_k - Z_T(\omega_k, P))^2 \quad (2.13)$$

Figure 11 Bode and Nyquist plots of frequency sweep for Randles circuit

Figure 12 Randles circuit reconstruction under the presence of random perturbations.

Where P is the set of Randles circuit parameters, y_k is the measure value of the impedance of the transducer at the test frequency ω_k . The Randles circuit impedance is,

$$Z_T(\omega, P) = R_S + \frac{Z_{cd}(\omega)(R_{ct} + Z_w(\omega))}{R_{ct} + Z_w(\omega) + Z_{cd}(\omega)} \quad (2.14)$$

Figure 12 depicts a reconstruction example of the Randles circuit impedance (equation 2.14) for a set of 10 simulated values of the impedance at 10 logarithmic spaced frequencies between 1Hz and 10kHz. The figure shows that the reconstruction using the trust-region-reflective algorithm is possible even in the presence of random variations, due to noise or parameter changes. The test was made assuming 10% and 1% standard deviation tests.

Figure 13 Absolute error trends for different number of samples.

Model reconstruction also depend on the number of measured samples. In order to have a clear idea on what the real performance can be, we made some simulations. These simulations assume the presence of random perturbations, following as before the 1% and 10% standard deviation as above and a Gaussian distribution. We run for each value of the number of samples, 1000 simulations in order to gain some statistical significance. The results depicted on figure 13, show that the average absolute error follows a decreasing trend when we increase the number of samples. Furthermore, even with a small number of samples, it is possible to infer with high accuracy the parameters of the Randles circuit, if the random perturbations are of small amplitude. The error bar plots show also the standard deviation (vertical bars) for each trial, which also decrease with the number of samples.

Fig. 14 – Nervous tissues stimulation approaches: a) electrical stimulation; b) chemical stimulation; c) optical stimulation.

3. NEURAL STIMULATION CONCEPTUAL SCHEMES

The stimulation of nervous tissues can take different approaches. These approaches are linked to the tissue reactions to the external stimulation. Nervous tissues are composed by biological substrates which exhibit specific responses to stimuli of different natures. As these responses are related to ionic interactions at the cell level, external interaction is possible either through the application of electrical signals, release of specific chemicals and even light pulses of specific wavelengths (Kim et al., 2019). Figure 14 depicts the conceptual diagrams associated to each of these possibilities. The next sections present and overview of these possibilities and high light their properties.

3.1. Electrical Stimulation

In electrical stimulation, the essence of the technique is to motivate the flow of ions in the cells. These can be accomplished using three possible approaches: direct coupling, capacitive coupling and inductive coupling. In direct coupling the ionic motion is motivated by the application of a voltage/current/charge signal to a pair of electrodes that directly interact with the cells (Kim et al., 2019). This is the most used method for high density neural implants, as it is the most amenable method to circuit integration (X. Li et al., 2017). Direct interaction with the cells raises some challenges and concerns, associated with biocompatibility of the electrode's materials or unwanted cell responses. In capacitive coupling, there is no direct contact with the cells. The ionic motion is achieved through the influence of an applied electrical field. This method implies the usage of two plate type electrodes in parallel configuration (similar to a capacitor). The cells are exposed to the electrical field between the plates. Another alternative is inductive coupling, where the electric field is replaced by a magnetic field in a coil like system. The cells are embedded within the coil axis. Both of these methods

Figure 14 - Conceptual circuits for voltage (a) and current stimulation (b).

prevent the direct contact with the cells, but demand highly complex infrastructures, not compatible with circuit integration (X. Li et al., 2017).

Electrical stimulation with direct coupling can adopt different forms concerning type of stimulus applied: voltage, current or charge. Current and charge are commonly preferred solutions for integrated circuit design as they are based on simple bidirectional current mirrors. High voltage compliance is a problem for these cases, as with current technologies the voltage headroom is low (current state-of-the-art CMOS processes operate with bias below 1V). However, as seen in the section 2, the dynamics of biological synapses exhibit an amplitude-time inverse relation which can be suitably exploited for the design of electrical stimulation circuits. The choice of current or charge stimulation is also a natural one, given that is often desirable to have a precise control over the current or charge transferred to the cells. This is explained by the limits that can be applied to charge and charge density during the stimulation (Cong, 2016). There is an experimental based Shannon criterion relating the charge and the charge density during stimulation, this criterion establishes limits for safe operation. Operating the stimulation above these limits implies damage to the cells (Cong, 2016). Voltage mode stimulation does not allow a direct control over the charge transferred to the cells. Thus, it implies the usage of additional current limitation circuitry, which further complicates the design

Figure 15 depicts the conceptual circuits for voltage a current stimulation. Starting with the voltage stimulation circuit, it is based on a conventional potentiostat used to test electrochemical cells (Bard and Faulkner, 2001). It is basically a feedback amplifying circuit design to force the input voltage V_i on the reference electrode (RE). In order to operate properly, the RE amplifier should exhibit a very high input impedance in order to induce minimal perturbation of the cell. Furthermore, the amplifier feeding the working electrode (WE) should have high voltage drive capabilities in order to handle large voltage variations implied by the cell. For safe stimulation, the system should consider a second feedback loop, controlled by a current sensing element. The current sensing control allows to prevent damage of the cells, by acting appropriately on the stimulus input. Current and charge stimulation operate on the same principle: direct current and current control. Possible implementations use bidirectional current sources such as the one depicted in figure 15. Current direction is controlled

through switches S_1 and S_2 , while current control is directed controlled through the sources (or current mirrors) I_A and I_C . The output voltage handling is constrained by the bias voltage V_{DD} . Charge control can be achieved with the same circuit by implementing a precise timing control circuit for the opening and closing of switches S_1 and S_2 . that charge is just the time integral of current), this is easily achieved with fixed amplitude current pulses. Given that charge is the time integral of the current, for a fixed amplitude current pulse, the charge transferred is simply the product of the pulse amplitude by the pulse duration. A suitable modification of this circuit, with just one current controlled source are possible using a H bridge to interface the electrodes (X. Li et al., 2017).

Electrode Materials	CSC (mC/cm ²)	Charge Injection limit (mC/cm ²)	Impedance @ 1 kHz (k Ω)	Electrode size (μ m ²)	Impedance /area (Ω/μ m ²)	Reference
Au	3.18	0.1	52	10000	5.2	(Bozkurt and Lal, 2011)
Pt	6.26	0.026	-	-	-	(Cisnal et al., 2018)
TiN	2.35	0.87	-	4000	-	(Weiland et al., 2002)
IrO_x	25	-	7.1	2400	3	(Han and McCreery, 2008)
PtIr	1.2	0.15	26.6	17000	1.6	(Vitale et al., 2015)
IrO_x/Pt	46.28	-	-	-	-	(Chung et al., 2018)
ITO	0.058	-	-	78.5	-	(Yang et al., 2018)
CNT fiber	372	6.52	14.1	1.45	9.7	(Vitale et al., 2015)
Graphene	50	3.2	0.519	90000	0.006	(Lu et al., 2016)
PEDOT	75.6	-	23.3	177	132	(Wilks et al., 2009)
Glassy Carbon	61.4	3	5.8	70650	0.08	(Nimbalkar et al., 2018)

Table 1 - Summary of electrode characteristics used for direct coupling electrical stimulation.

Another important aspect related to electrical stimulation, and especially with the electrodes is the charge storage capacity (CSC), that is, the total charge available at the electrode per unite area. The goal of any stimulation system is to maximize the CSC, this encompasses the selection of electrode materials. The choice of a particular materials has implications on the electrochemical impedance, and thus, with overall performance of the stimulation unit (Kim et al., 2019). Different materials have different values of CSC and produce different electrochemical impedance levels. Electro-deposited iridium oxide is one of the most used materials for electrodes, with a CSC sufficiently high (25 mC/cm²). Other materials based on carbon nanotubes and graphene exhibit higher CSC but with lower charge injection limits. Table 1 summarizes the characteristics of some materials used for electrodes.

3.2. Optical Stimulation

Optical stimulation exploits the optical response of nervous tissues, and in particular, neurons (Kim et al., 2019). This is the focus of optogenetics, with the aim to address high spatial resolution stimulation of neural cells using light. Neurons are naturally insensitive to light, but once they are genetically modified with opsins, they can become sensitive. Excitation and inhibition are two approaches followed for neural stimulation. This genetic modification can be achieved using light-sensitive proteins. For instance, using channelrhodopsin-2 (ChR2) turns neurons sensitive to blue light (~473 nm), while halorhodopsin (NpHR) triggers sensitivity to yellow light (~590 nm). ChR2 is used for excitation while NpHR is used for inhibition (Kim et al., 2019). The neural probes for optical stimulation used LEDs (light-emitting diodes) or laser diodes (LD) with wavelengths matched to the proteins' sensitivity peaks. Table 2 summarizes examples of optical probes developed for optical stimulation of neurons.

Protein (color)	Light Source	Wavelength (nm)	Power	Device size (μm^2)	Reference
-	Laser	473/593	1.35 mW – 473nm 3.6 mW - 593nm	-	(Rubehn et al., 2011)
ChR2 (blue)	Laser	473	51 mW/mm ²	70	(Wu et al., 2013)
ChR2 (blue)	μ LED	675/530/450	17.7/23.5 mW/mm ²	2500	(Kim et al., 2013)
ChR2 (blue)	Laser	475	500 mW/mm ²	300	(Son et al., 2015)
ChR2 (blue)	μ LED	460	353 mW/mm ²	150	(Wu et al., 2015)
ArchT (green)	Laser	550	1.52 mW	1.963	(Kim et al., 2015)
-	LD	650	96.9 mW/mm ²	195	(Schwaerzle et al., 2017)

Table 2 - Summary of multifunctional probes for optical stimulation.

Optical stimulation is out of scope of project NeuroStimSpinal. From the point of view of stimulation technologies and circuit design considerations, it can be a promising candidate for future research. Using optical means for stimulation offers several interesting possibilities:

- Reduced power consumption, as the power required for stimulation is not dependent on the impedance of the tissues.
- Indirect access method, as the electrodes may not need to be in contact with the nerves. In this sense, the scaffold could embed biocompatible light-sensitive materials, that would produce an optical response in reaction to an external stimulus. The external stimulus could be applied externally, exploiting sub-cutaneous optical transmission to the scaffold.
- Reduced the need to external devices.

These possibilities are at this stage based on research on optical transdermal communications (Ghassemlooy et al., 2017). The goal for these systems is to establish secure communications links with implantable devices, such as pacemakers. Research results so far, disclosed the possibility to communicate wirelessly with transcutaneous devices. Studies have also addressed the characteristics of the medium, human dermis, quantifying the attenuation to optical wavelengths.

3.3. Chemical Stimulation

Chemical stimulation explores the chemical interaction between neural cells. These interactions are linked to the action potentials (electrical signals), but also to the exchange of neurotransmitters. This raises the possibility to use specific chemicals to trigger neural responses (Kim et al., 2019). There are two main drug delivery mechanisms in use for chemical stimulation: pressure driven (or displacement driven) microfluidic delivery; and electrochemical controlled release. Microfluidics systems, such as mixers and valves, have been used for drug delivery with success. Electrochemical release involves the usage of electrodes specific design to release the chemical drugs from their surface. Table 3 presents a summary of probes developed for chemical stimulation of neural cells.

Delivery method	Features	Materials for channel	Chemicals	Drug mixing	In vivo test	Reference
Microfluidic	-	LPCVD/thermal dielectrics	Kainic acid, GABA	-	Yes	(Jingkuang Chen et al., 1997)
Microfluidic	-	Parylene	Evans blue, albumin	-	Yes	(Neeves et al., 2006)
Microfluidic	Micropump, reservoir	Silicon	-	-	No	(Park et al., 2008)
Microfluidic	Pressure reservoir	Silicon nitride	Hoechst 33342, propidium iodide, HEPES buffer, glucose	-	Yes	(Retterer et al., 2008)
Microfluidic	Microfluidic chip	silicon	Pilocarpine, tetrodoxin, saline, DAPI	Yes	Yes	(Shin et al., 2015)
Microfluidic	Fluidic channel	Borosilicate	Saline, muscimol, aCSF	-	Yes	(Dagdeviren et al., 2018)
Electrochemical	PEDOT	No channel	Dexamethasone	-	Yes	(Boehler et al., 2017)
Electrochemical	Polypyrrole	No channel	Dexamethasone phosphate, meropenem	-	No	(Shah et al., 2018)

Table 3 - Summary of multifunctional chemical stimulation probes.

4. ELECTRICAL STIMULATION SPECIFICATION'S

This section presents a state of the art on electrical stimulation of nervous tissues with highlight on three techniques: direct coupling, capacitive coupling and inductive coupling. For each technique, the study focused the characteristics of the applied stimuli and the results achieved in terms of morphology of the cells under stimulation. This initial study provides information for the development of the stimulation unit. Relevant information such as: shape of the stimulus, amplitude and frequency, recurrence and duration of the trials, are essential for design considerations. Equipped with this information, the other section focuses on the development of an in-vitro stimulation-acquisition unit, and an in-vivo stimulation unit. For the in-vitro unit, the design approach considers the usage of commercial off the shelf components, and less demanding restriction in terms of power consumption, voltage-current capabilities and size. It also includes the option for electrical signal acquisition, which though not part of the project, may lead to important contribution for the state of the art on the field of the project. The in-vivo unit poses some design challenges linked to power consumption, size and current-voltage capabilities. The design approach for this unit involves integrated circuit design capabilities in order to handle size constraints.

4.1. State-of-the-art Assessment

There are 3 main methods of delivering the stimulus to neural cells (Balint et al., 2013):

Direct coupling: the electrode is in direct contact with the cell culture or implanted into the animal. This approach has some disadvantages: i) Toxicity due to incompatibility of electrodes material; ii) pH changes; iii) Molecular reduction; and iv) Generation of Faradaic byproducts.

Capacitive coupling: an electric field is created between the two layers of the plate capacitor. The distance between the plates varies depending on the culture's size in the middle. Some of the advantages of this type of coupling are mainly: avoiding most of the inconvenient environmental changes introduced by direct coupling and generate a homogeneous electric field, which affects all the cells in the same way.

Inductive coupling: The cell culture is placed in the center of one or more coils that generate a magnetic field. Pulsed magnetic field stimulation (PEMF) is a specific type of an inductive coupling, where there's a pulsed stimulus instead of a static or sinusoidal.

Table 1 compares these different stimulation approaches. Direct stimulation is mainly used to influence the morphology and orientation of cells. Capacitive stimulation seems to be more effective in increasing proliferation, while cells treated with inductive stimuli display greater embryonic stem cell (ECM) deposition. There is also the possibility of mixing the modalities like it was done by Brighton (Brighton et al., 2001) with MC3T3-E1 clonal osteoblastic cells applying and comparing 3 modalities: conductive (0.002V/mm sinewave at 60 Hz for 0.5–24 h), inductive (22.5 – 2.5G pulses in 15 Hz bursts for 0.5–24 h) and combined (340 – 140mG static and 370 – 47 mG, 76.6 Hz alternating field for 0.5–24 h). The results showed increment in DNA content for all of the modalities but some effects on Ca²⁺ varied between them. Table 1 presents also relevant information concerning the type and characteristics of the stimulation signals. Depending on the type of cells there are limits for electrical specifications and there are thresholds that can result in cell death (e.g., 20 μ A in the case of nonunions). A wide range of frequencies (7.5-60k Hz) have been applied in some experiments but most

of them were under 100 Hz, which makes sense according to in vivo natural processes. It is especially important to understand the type of cells under stimulation to provide an appropriated stimulus (Gulrez et al., 2011).

Article	Cell types	Stimulation	Results
Direct coupling:			
(Schmidt et al., 1997a)	Rat PC-12 cells	0.1V with 10 mA for 2 h using a Polypyrrole - (PPy) film as anode	Stimulation on the PPy film produced significantly larger neurite length than in unstimulated and tissue culture plastic control groups.
(Serena et al., 2009)	Human ESC line H13	1V/mm at 1Hz	Spontaneous contractions, expression, and sarcomnetric organization
(Shi et al., 2008)	Human cutaneous fibroblasts	0.05V/mm DC for 24–48 h using a PPy/PLLA conductor	Cells adhered, spread and proliferated on the conductors
(Sun et al., 2006)	Rat bone marrow MSCs	0.2, 0.4, and 0.7V/mm DC for 0–60 min on Coll. Type I gel	Cytokine production enhanced 10-fold by stimulation; Changes in morphology observed with both MSCs and fibroblasts, but only the latter aligned in response to the stimulus.
(Radisic et al., 2004)	Rat fibroblasts HT1080; Neonatal rat ventricular myocytes	0.5 V/mm, 2ms rectangular pulses at 1Hz	Stimulation resulted in alignment and coupling, increased amplitude contractions, and enhanced ultrastructural organization.
Capacitive coupling:			
(Au et al., 2007)	Neonatal rat; cardiomyocytes and NIH3T3 fibroblasts	0.23 and 0.43V/mm, 1ms rectangular pulses at 1Hz	Stimulation enhanced elongation of both cell types and fibroblast alignment on abraded surfaces. Topographical cues were stronger.
(Hartig et al., 2000)	Bovine primary osteoblasts	6 V/mm, 62.5 ms sawtooth pulses at 16 Hz for 5-18 days	Significant increase in proliferation in nonconfluent and enhanced ECM related protein secretion in confluent cultures.
(Kim et al., 2006)	Rat calvarial osteoblasts	1.5 mA/cm ² biphasic el. current at 3000 Hz for 6 h or 24 h/day	Higher proliferation in continuously stimulated samples. No change in ALP, osteopontin, coll. Type I, BMP-2, -4, IGF-2, and TGF-b1 levels.
(Kim et al., 2008)	Human bone marrow MSCs	1.5 mA/cm ² biphasic el current at 100Hz for 24 h/day for 7 days	Proliferation increased by 57%. No increase in osteoblast differentiation. Stimulation induced VEGF expression.
(Kim et al., 2009)	Human MSCs	1.5 or 15 mA/cm ² biphasic current 250/25 ms at 100 Hz for 7 days	Increased proliferation. ALP activity and calcium deposition enhanced after stimulation. Expression of VEGF and BMP-2.
(Zhuang et al., 1997)	MC3T3-E1 clonal osteoblastic cells	0.002V/mm, 300 mA/cm ² sine signal at 60 kHz for 30 min-24 h	Stimulation enhanced proliferation and increased the levels of TGF-b1.
Inductive coupling:			
(Bodamyali et al., 1998)	Neonatal rat calvarial osteoblasts	1G, 0.225 ms pulses in 4.5 ms bursts for 6 h	Exposure significantly increased the number and size of deposited bone-like

			nodules. Enhanced BMP-2 and BMP-4 expression.
(Lohmann et al., 2003)	MLO-Y4 osteocyte-like cells ROS 17/2.8 cell line	16G sawtooth pulses in 4.5 ms bursts at 15 Hz for 8h/day	Increased ALP activity, TGF- β 1, and prostaglandin E2 expression, while osteocalcin or cell numbers went unchanged.
(McLeod et al., 1993)	Osteosarcoma cell line ROS 17/2.8	0.0018 T at 30Hz for 12 or 72 h	Exposure limited the normal increase in cell numbers, while enhanced ALP activity. Effects were cell density dependent.
(Molen et al., 2000)	Osteosarcoma cell line ROS 17/2.8	0.0018 T at 30Hz for 120 h	Stimulation inhibited cell growth. ALP activity was dependent on gap junctional coupling. Results suggest differential effects.

Table 4 - Different stimulation techniques based on Blint et al., 2013. ESC, embryonic stem cell; MSC, mesenchymal stem cell; ROS, reactive oxygen species; ECM, extracellular matrix; TGF transforming growth factor; ALP, alkaline phosphatase; VEGF, vascular endothelial growth factor.

4.2. In-Vitro Stimulation System Specification

Following the state-of-the-art review for electrical stimulation and considering the discussion on the previous sections, this section draws the specification of the in-vitro stimulation circuit. The circuit architecture that will be adopted for the in-vitro stimulation unit will rely on the following characteristics:

- Electrical stimulation with direct coupling.
- Support current/charge stimulation and control.
- Support multimode pulsed waveforms (periodical, bursts, and single shot).
- Support high compliance voltages.
- Support stimulation of multiple cell cultures.
- Support electrical signal acquisition (cell's voltage).
- Based on commercial off the shelf components.

Table 5 summarizes the characteristics of the system, providing a quantitative description of the main characteristics, concerning operation limits, resolutions and features.

Characteristics	In-Vitro	In-Vivo
Mode (current/voltage)	Current	Current
Amplitude range	1 -200 μ A	0.1 – 20 mA
DC value control	yes	yes
Amplitude resolution	0.5 μ A	50 μ A
Maximum Compliance	25 V	5 V (tolerant)
Stimulus shape	Square pulses	Square pulses
Frequency	1 Hz – 100 kHz	1 Hz – 100 kHz
Duty-cycle control	Yes	Yes
Timing mode	Periodic/burst/pulsed	Periodic/burst/pulsed
Time resolution	20 μ s	20 μ s
N^o Channels	32	4
Acquisition support	Voltage	No support
Design approach	COTS components	ASIC

Table 5 - In-vitro and in-vivo system specification summary.

4.3. In-Vivo Stimulation System Specification

Following the state of the art review for electrical stimulation and considering the discussion on the previous sections, this section draws the specification of the in-vivo stimulation circuit. The circuit architecture that will be adopted for the in-vivo stimulation unit will rely on the following characteristics:

- Electrical stimulation with direct coupling.
- Support current/charge stimulation and control.
- Support multimode pulsed waveforms (periodical, bursts, and single shot).
- Based on an application specific integrated circuit (ASIC).

Table 5 summarizes the characteristics of the system, providing a quantitative description of the main characteristics, concerning operation limits, resolutions and features.

5. ELECTRODE'S MATERIALS AND GEOMETRIES

Several lines of research are currently directed towards the development of advanced electrodes that can be reliably safe and sensitive. The amount and diversity of such electrodes seem almost unlimited since different applications demand different electrode types with respect to their size, invasiveness, selectivity, materials and performance. Some important considerations are:

- For every electrode there is an intrinsic charge injection capacity (CIC), restricting the voltage that can be safely generated at the electrode's surface. Beyond this electrochemical limit, also known as the water-window, irreversible electrolysis of water can result in tissue damage, electrode dissolution, pH variations and production of unwanted species. (Aryan et al., 2015; Harris et al., 2018; Wellman et al., 2018)
- To generate an effective electrical stimulation, it is crucial to select new electrode geometries/sizes, materials and/or coatings in order to increase the charge transfer surface area such that the charge injection safety limits are preserved.
- Biocompatible, corrosion-resistive materials for electrical recording and stimulation include gold, titanium, tungsten, platinum, iridium oxide, stainless steel, alloys of the mentioned metals, highly doped semiconductors such as silicon, and conductive polymers. Lately, several electrodes have been improved by modification of the surface chemistry with carbon-based coatings, as well as with biological ones. (Kim and Romero-Ortega, 2012).
- The current development towards smaller electrodes to improve spatial resolution present another set of problems, as they must withstand a higher voltage to transport the same charge per area than a larger electrode in order to induce the same response. (Harris et al., 2018) Smaller electrodes enhance the applied charge density, as they inevitably suffer from high electrical impedance and consequent high thermal noise, leading to potential tissue damage and of the electrodes themselves, and thus deteriorating the signal-to-noise ratio. (Aryan et al., 2015; Boehler et al., 2015)

The most well-established type of electrodes consists of an assembled array of metallic (gold, platinum, and titanium) microelectrodes (10-200 μm in diameter), fabricated by complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) technology, passivated (to work in a liquid environment) and connected to an external measurement unit – the so-called MicroElectrode Array (MEA). MEAs have been studied for decades and are typically fabricated on rigid substrates (e.g., quartz, silicon, sapphire, glass, etc.) and difficult to combine with soft tissue, due to their high mechanical mismatch. A specific type of MEAs that have been used as stimulation electrodes, as well as for the recording of an electroneurogram in the area of functional electrical stimulation are the multielectrode cuffs. Cuff electrodes have an established story for long-term recording of neural activity – up to 63 weeks after implantation in human volunteers. (Fisher et al., 2009) Cuff electrodes typically encloses the nerve with flexible and self-sizing silicone or polyimide that avoid stretching or compression damage of the enclosed nerve. On the other hand, when two individually addressable microelectrodes array strips are integrated onto the same plane with an interdigitate approach, they are designated as planar InterDigitated Electrodes (IDE). (Ahadian et al., 2012; Lim et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2017) This type of electrodes generates stimulation under low voltage and in a direct, effective, highly reproducible and controlled manner. IDEs are widely utilized in technological applications, particularly in the field of biological and chemical sensors due to their inexpensiveness, ease of fabrication process and high sensitivity. MEA are part of

Figure 15 - Different types of PNI according to their sensitivity and invasiveness. (Kim and Romero-Ortega, 2012)

a group of peripheral nerve interfacing (PNI) electrodes. In fact, PNI can be both extraneural (e.g. Cuff electrodes) or intraneural (e.g. MEA). Intraneural electrodes are placed directly in the peripheral nerves and their proximity provides increased neural selectivity and sensitivity. According to the specific mode of intraneural electrode placement within the nerve tissue, the scientific community recognizes four major electrode designs (Kim and Romero-Ortega, 2012):

- Longitudinally Implanted Intrafascicular Electrodes (LIFE) – limitations include drift in the population of cells being recorded and a decrease in signal-to-noise ratio over time;
- Transverse Intrafascicular Multi-channel Electrodes (TIME) – which penetrates the peripheral nerve and is designed to selectively activate different fascicles within the nerve;
- Coiled Wire Intrafascicular Electrodes (CWIE) – made from nylon-coated stainless-steel wire and is wound into helical flexible coils to allow for expansion and contraction within the surrounding nerve tissue; and
- Utah Slanted Electrode Array (USEA) – a version of MEA but made of needle electrodes of varying lengths (0.5 to 1.5 mm with 0.1 mm difference in length between rows of neighboring electrodes) designed to access most fascicles within the nerve.

A specific subset of intraneural PNIs are regenerative electrodes, which are based on an alternative design to penetrating electrodes and are used for the spontaneously regrowth of peripheral nerves after injury. In general, the sensitivity of regenerative electrodes is superior to that of extraneural electrodes. However, their implantation requires invasive surgery, which might be justified in most amputee cases (Kim and Romero-Ortega, 2012). There are three types of regenerative electrodes:

- Sieve electrodes – can be either ring or needle shaped placed between two ends of the cut nerve. Can originate nerve compression injury.;
- Regenerative Multielectrode Interface (REMI) – placed between the transected ends of an end-to-end repaired nerve. Does not restrict the growth of the nerve, and thus the nerve compression injury typically observed for Sieve electrodes does not occur.
- Microchannel Roll Electrode (MCRE) – rolled into a 3D channel bundle and designed to fit the transected peripheral nerve at both ends of the roll.

All the above mentioned PNI suffer from limitations, particularly in terms of safe reliability, as well as sensitivity. (Kim and Romero-Ortega, 2012) distributed the different types of PNI according to their sensitivity and invasiveness (see Figure 15). For the authors, sensitivity is related to the electrode's ability to record action potentials, while invasiveness relates to the damage to the nerve while placing the electrode.

The purpose of this essay is to describe the use of different kinds of electrodes, taking into consideration a set of important features that may interfere with the cell stimulation when using electrical fields, namely: 1) its composition, such as the material and surface treatment (metal, inorganic and organic coatings, and surface biological molecules); and 2) configuration, such as area, format (MEA, interdigitated or spiral cuff) or shape (3D scaffold hybrids). A summary of the systems presented on the next lines of this documents (i.e., materials along with their electrical stimulation paradigm) used for electrical stimulation is then presented on Table 6.

5.1. METAL Electrodes

Typical platinum, gold and platinum-iridium are used for fabricating biomedical electrodes. (Dmitry Kireev et al., 2016) Platinum has historically been considered the preferred metal used for electrodes in neuroprostheses. (Aregueta-Robles et al., 2014) However, there are electrical, mechanical and biological aspects of these electrodes that remain as limiting factors and prevent their application on high-density microelectrode arrays for neural interfacing. In the literature, the limitations associated with this type of electrodes' performance have been addressed through several and varied approaches, which include passivation and surface texturing to reduce impedance and enhance tissue integration.

For instance, organic and inorganic coatings (including platinum-black, titanium nitride, and iridium oxide) have been used to increase the charge injection capacity of metallic electrodes. (Aregueta-Robles et al., 2014) For instance, a commercial MEA based on titanium nitride (TiN) typically exhibits a value of 0.11 mC/cm² (impedance in the range 30–400 k Ω) (Gomes et al., 2019) and platinum electrodes allows 300–350 mC/cm², while electrodes coated with iridium oxide (IrOx) have a capacity of 2–3 mC/cm², being safer as it prevents tissue electrolytic damage. (Kim and Romero-Ortega, 2012) However, electrode coatings like IrOx have additionally been reported to be brittle or prone to delaminate, further restricting their use. (Aregueta-Robles et al., 2014; Thaning et al., 2010).

5.2. Platinum Electrodes

Although there is no electrical stimulation of cells reported, (Boehler et al., 2015) described the use nanostructured platinum grass coating, enabling superior impedance reduction for neural microelectrodes (with sizes between 5 and 500 μ m). The coating was applied via a simple electrochemical process on silicon wafer. The cell studies were performed using human neuroblastoma cell line SH-SY5Y and this sterile culture medium was exposed to the coating surfaces at three different concentrations, 1.25 cm²/mL, 2 cm²/mL and 3.2 cm²/mL, for 24h at 37°C. The stability of the coating was also assessed during two weeks by applying a rectangular current pulse with 200 nC/phase at a frequency of 200 Hz. Curiously, the values reported for the impedance (at 100 Hz) were found to be lower than IrOx and PEDOT:PSS (a conductive polymer), while the CIC was where the lowest improvement was attained.

(Harris et al., 2018) prepared a set of electrodes by mechanically polishing platinum with different sizes (2 mm, 0.6 mm, or 25 μ m of diameter) and the charge density proved to be dependent on the charge injection capacity and electrode area, ranging from 0.15 to 5.57 mC/cm².

(Ahadian et al., 2012) applied a pulsed voltage stimulation on muscle tissue using a platinum electrode and observed a higher level of C2C12 muscle tube alignment (>80%) and muscle transcription factors, among others benefits. The stimulation was performed through an IDE using electrical pulse of 6 V, 1 Hz and duration of 10 ms for 1 day. The results demonstrated superior performance and maturation compared with a conventional setup (platinum wires in close proximity).

(Pfau et al., 2019) studied the influence of standard clinical electrical pulsing on flexible polyimide-based thin-film platinum macro (338 and 444 μm) and micro (85 μm) electrodes for neuroprostheses, either sputter-deposited or evaporated. These electrodes were stressed with 120 million current controlled biphasic, cathodic-first, charge balanced pulses with a charge density of 60 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ / phase and a frequency of 500 Hz in 0.01 M PBS in vitro. Only sputtered electrodes with 88 μm showed the cathodic potential excursion starting about the 160 mV within the safe limit of water electrolysis.

On an interesting work, (Rozman et al., 2014) investigated the electrochemical performance of platinum electrodes within a multi-electrode spiral cuff by testing it to selectively stimulate isolated porcine left cervical vagus nerve segment. The original cuff was simplified into a half-cuff and contained a single row of nine electrodes (0.5 x 2 mm) at 2 mm from its inner surface. Charge injection capacity of the electrode was around 75 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ and the results showed that both the most negative and positive potentials across the electrode-electrolyte interface reached -0.54 and 0.59 V, respectively, not exceeding the safe potential limits for water electrolysis.

5.3. Gold Electrodes

Although without describing a procedure for electrical stimulation of cells, (Vafaiee et al., 2019) reported a simple and cost-effective method for the fabrication of gold multielectrode arrays with high scratch strength for electrophysiological recordings. The authors described an enhancement on the adhesion of noble metals as gold and silver to glass substrates, as they typically are damaged while exposed to water-based medium.

(McCullen et al., 2010) used a gold electrode with interdigitated shape to deliver stimulation under alternating (AC) electric field of 1 V/cm, 4h for 14 days, and the results showed an increase in cellular osteogenic differentiation potential of human adipose-derived stem cells (hASCs).

(Körbitzer et al., 2019) prepared 0.31 mm² electrodes with pure gold (along with graphene on gold and graphene/SiO₂, which is presented latter on this document) to electrical stimulate cryo-conserved embryonic cortical rat neurons and found a charge injection capacity of 0.03 C/cm². Moreover, at frequencies between 1 Hz and 1 MHz, the lowest impedance value found was 7 k Ω .

5.4. ORGANIC Electrodes

In particular, the use of carbon allotropes (like carbon nanotubes, graphene, etc.), and conductive polymers (like Polypyrrole, PEDOT, Polyaniline, etc.) have shown that tailored approaches can be used to create microelectrode arrays (MEA) which not only improve the electrode material properties, but also provide biomolecules to aid in the establishment of a chronically stable neural interface. Organic coatings hold a significant benefit over the inorganic coatings as they can be easily modified to include functional molecules to influence the biological behavior. (Aregueta-Robles et al., 2014).

5.4.1. Conductive polymers-based electrodes

Electrode coatings, particularly polymeric films which utilize conductive polymers, have been shown to bear a softer electrode interface and can be used to diminish or mediate the mechanical difference between a metal electrode and the tissue with which it interfaces. Polypyrrole (PPy) along with poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT) and polyaniline (PANI) are among the conjugated polymers

with higher conductivity that have been used as high-performance biomaterials for cell electrical stimulation.

5.4.2. Polypyrrole

To deliver effective electrical stimulation for reversing the neurite outgrowth induced by dysregulation of risk genes neuregulin-1 (NRG1) and disrupted in schizophrenia 1 (DISC1) loss-of-function in prefrontal cortical (PFC) neural cells in mice, (Zhang et al., 2017) used the conductive polymer polypyrrole PPy. The cells were stimulated at ± 0.25 mA/cm² using a biphasic waveform of 100 μ m pulses with 20 μ m interphase open circuit potential and a 3.78 ms short circuit (250 Hz). (Liu et al., 2018) also prepared PPy planar electrodes to regulate cellular osteogenic differentiation through an electrical stimulation of MC3T3-E1 cells seeded at a density of 2×10^4 cells per cm². In this work, the charge injection quantity (Q_{inj}) proved to be an important parameter, since when the cells were electrically stimulated for 1 hour per day, 0.08–0.15 μ C had an obvious role in enhancing cellular osteogenic differentiation, while Q_{inj} lower than 0.03 or higher than 0.30 μ C produced stimulations with no or negative effects. In this case, the frequency of stimulation (applied voltages of 5 mV) also played an important role, as 1 or 25 Hz showed to enhance differentiation, whereas the stimulation with 50 Hz gave an inhibiting effect. Other relevant studies using PPy were presented by (Cui et al., 2001; Kim et al., 2004; Stewart et al., 2015)

5.4.3. PEDOT

ReNcellVM Neural Stem Cells (NSC) were differentiated by electrical stimulation using a cross-linked PEDOT substrate for the first time by (Pires et al., 2015). NSC were seeded (140 000 cells/cm²) in laminin coated surfaces, cultured for 4 days and differentiated over 8 additional days under 100 Hz pulsed DC electrical stimulation, 1V with 10 ms pulses. In this work, the population of neurons (Tuj1) was 1.6 times higher with longer neurites (73 vs. 108 μ m) for cells cultured under electrical stimulus with cultured NSC.

(Carli et al., 2019) used fluorinated polymer Nafion as counter ion instead of PSS (polystyrene-sulfonate) to fabricate an electrodeposited PEDOT:Nafion composite for neural recording and stimulation. The PEDOT:Nafion coated electrodes provide a large signal-to-noise ratio in a murine animal model (when compared to PEDOT:PSS) as a result of a minimized polarization during electrical stimulation, thereby resulting in an improved charge injection limit equal to 4.4 mC/cm². This value is almost 80% larger than the 2.5 mC/cm² observed for PEDOT:PSS. The electrodes used in this study had a 140 μ m diameter, so a charge density of 0.5 mC/cm² would correspond to a current amplitude of 154 μ A for a stimulating pulse of 500 μ s.

(Schander et al., 2016) reported an in vitro evaluation of the long-term stability of PEDOT-coated circular gold microelectrodes (with approximately 560 μ m of diameter, $A = 0.25$ mm²). The electrodes were coated using a galvanostatic electropolymerization process. The continuous stimulation consisted of a bipolar current amplitude of 5 mA, a pulse duration of 100 μ s per phase, an interphase gap (pulse pause) of 50 μ s and a frequency of 1 kHz. This corresponded to 86.4 million bipolar current pulses per day at a current density of 2A/cm². Other relevant studies using PPy were presented by (Richardson-Burns et al., 2007; Wilks et al., 2009).

5.4.4. PANI

Self-doped sulfonated polyaniline (SPANI)-based interdigitated electrodes (IDEs) for controlled electrical stimulation of human osteosarcoma (HOS) cells were studied by (Min et al., 2013). The electrode exhibited good cell attachment and proliferation under in vitro mild electrical stimulation. The authors claimed that the conductivity of the copolymer increased with the degree of the

sulfonation (DS) and described an increased number of HOS cells when DS increased from 0% to 50%. The experimental results also unveiled that a further increase above this DS led to a marginal decrease in both the conductivity of the SPAN and the HOS cell count, due to possible increased solubility of SPAN in aqueous medium. The electrical stimulation was performed varying both voltage and frequency. When the applied voltage or the frequency was increased by keeping the other constant at 800 mV or 1 kHz, an increased HOS cell count was found. (Min et al., 2013) also declared the existence of a threshold for the cell growth at an applied voltage (1200 mV) or frequency (200 kHz). Cell death was observed by the authors above these threshold limits. Other relevant studies using PANI were presented by (Thrivikraman et al., 2015, 2014; Wang et al., 2015)

5.5. Carbon-based electrodes

Better integration of tissues and neural electrodes can be achieved by “humanizing” the material, i.e., making it structurally and chemically more similar to tissues surrounding neurons. Carbon-based electrodes have remarkable mechanical and electrical properties that exhibit a notable interaction with neural tissue. While there is number of methods that can be used to yield carbon coatings film processing in substrates for neural growth, not all of them are consensually accepted for stimulation purposes, including simple solvent evaporation, polyelectrolyte layering, chemical vapor deposition (CVD) and electrochemical deposition.

5.5.1. CNT

Several studies (Aregueta-Robles et al., 2014) on electrodes coated with carbon nanotubes (CNTs) report a substantial increase in signal-to-noise ratio for recording electrodes predominantly due to the low impedance CNTs imparting to the electrodes. CNTs are tubes made of carbon with diameters typically measured in nanometers and exhibit remarkable electrical conductivity, as well as exceptional tensile strength and thermal conductivity because of their nanostructure and strength of the bonds between carbon atoms. The safe charge injection limit of CNT-containing coatings has been reported to be between 1.6 and 2.5 mC/cm². This is more than 10 times the charge injection reported for platinum. However, (Burbles et al., 2016) increased the thickness of a coating containing CNT and a CSC has been reported to be as high as 70 mC/cm².

Although potential cytotoxicity of CNT remains a controversial issue, (Mooney et al., 2012) previously demonstrated no adverse effects on mesenchymal stem cell (MSC) behavior at low concentrations of both single and multiwalled nanotubes. (Mooney et al., 2012) exposed MSC to a medium containing CNT and seeded (with a density of 20 000 cells/cm²) MSC on a CNT-based polylactic acid scaffolds, while electrically stimulating them in an electrophysiological bioreactor. The electrical stimulation was carried out using a current of 0.15V/cm for 2 ms at a frequency of 1Hz for more than 10 days. The authors observed that the majority of the cells exposed to the medium containing CNT or seeded on the CNT-based scaffolds reorient perpendicularly to the electrical current at an angle between 0° and 10° and adopted an elongated morphology.

(Kam et al., 2009) fabricated CNT thin films via a layer-by-layer method with alternating layers of single walled CNT (SWCNT) and the protein laminin to stimulate NSC cells. The conductivity of a 10-bilayer SWCNT/laminin thin film was estimated to be 430 and 2140 S/m before and after heat treatment, respectively. The NSC cell response appeared to be, independent of the type of stimulus applied, though the employed signals consisted of a series (~10-15) of 1 ms pulses spaced in 1-10 s intervals. The pulses were applied to allow both the electrodes and the cells to discharge. Cellular stimulations were carried out over areas of the films of about 4 cm², and output currents from the film range from the order of 1-10 μA/cm².

(Lin et al., 2009) were the first researchers to grow CNTs electrode arrays (CNT-MEA) on a silicon substrate, transfer it onto a flexible and biocompatible polymeric film (Parylene-C), and then successfully record the APs of crayfish nerve cords. The reported dimensions of the flexible CNTs planar electrode were: 1) an opening area of the electrode site of $1962.5 \mu\text{m}^2$; and 2) a length of the conducting wire of $8100 \mu\text{m}$. The measurements presented by the authors demonstrated the superior performance of the flexible CNTs electrode with low impedance ($11.07 \text{ k}\Omega @ 1 \text{ kHz}$) and high peak-to-peak amplitude action potential (about 410 V). In addition, the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the flexible CNTs electrode is approximately 257, whereas the SNR of the reference (a pair of Teflon-coated silver wires) is only 79. The crayfish nerve cord was stimulated by a square pulse (amplitude of 7 V , and pulse duration of 0.1 ms) every 5 ms during the test, and then the action potential was recorded by the presented CNTs electrode and the reference electrode.

(Huang et al., 2012) synthesized CNT by CVD and prepared it into a ropelike structure with a diameter of 1 mm and length of 1.5 cm . This CNT rope substrate was then used to allow the electrical stimulation of differentiated neural stem cells (NSCs) in a culture medium and the in situ observation of the response of these stem cells after stimulation. The authors declared that the use of an electrical stimulation (5 mV , 0.5 mA , 25 ms intermittent) promoted a neuronal maturity, while also increasing the speed of neurite outgrowth. The intermittent stimulation instead of constant stimulation was performed to protect cells from constant electrical stress.

Another flexible MEA, completely made from CNTs that have been embedded in a polymeric support, has been presented by (David-Pur et al., 2014). This device showed the same characteristics as planar CNTs-MEAs, combined with the advantages of being flexible and consisting on a continuous rough surface. Actually, this paper has a great summary on CNT-MEAs on rigid and flexible substrates. (Shein et al., 2009) developed CNT-MEAs with improved electrochemical properties by synthesizing CNT "islands" on SiO_2 , and confirmed the capability of the device for recording the spontaneous activity of cultured rat cortical neurons. Focal electrical stimulations were applied to individual electrodes by delivering voltage biphasic (positive-then-negative) pulses, 500 mV in amplitude, with each phase lasting $400 \mu\text{s}$. A stimulation session was composed of 60 pulses separated by 20 s intervals.

Although without describing a procedure for electrical stimulation of cells, (Gabriel et al., 2013) reported the preparation of CNT MEAs, by depositing CNTs by CVD on platinum to grow ganglion cells in rabbit retinas onto uncoated P35 culture dishes.

5.5.2. Graphene

Graphene has many promising features such as biocompatibility, intrinsic flexibility and excellent electrical properties, allowing applications in the high-frequency regime. In some cases, the transparency of graphene also provides possibilities for the development of new tools for optogenetics. (D. Kireev et al., 2016; Kuzum et al., 2014; Park et al., 2014) Researchers have only recently begun to investigate graphene and its derivatives as potential scaffolds for neuronal growth. Graphene has attracted a generalized interest due to its excellent conductive properties, but also because its nanostructure and its chemical stability render it a good candidate for favoring cell adhesion. (Monaco and Giugliano, 2014) In vitro studies, carried out on human cell lines (i.e., HepG2, BEAS-2B, PC12, hMSCs), have demonstrated that the cyto- and genotoxicity of graphene depends on the dose, shape, and size of the nanomaterial itself, as well as on the presence of metal contaminants, oxides and/or residues of the graphene oxidation (graphene oxide) preparation method in samples.

For instance, the surface charges on graphene substrates has been investigated by (Tu et al., 2014), who cultured primary rat hippocampal neurons on carboxylated GO (GO-COOH ; negative surface

charge; control condition), the surface of which had been chemically modified by functionalization with three functional groups: methoxy (-OCH₃; nearly neutral surface charge), amino (NH₂; positively charged surface) and poly-m-aminobenzene sulfonic acid (-NH₂/-SO₃H, PABS; zwitterionic). Although no relevant differences in morphology were observed, neurons cultured on a positively charged surface showed a greater number of neurites per neuron, a longer length of neurites and a greater number of branches per neurite.

The use of graphene as an *in vitro* or an *in vivo* stimulator device was the primary focus of a study conducted by (Heo et al., 2011) who developed a graphene/PET film to test the effects of a non-contact field stimulation on cell-to-cell coupling. This film was found to be biocompatible and improved SHSY5Y human neuroblastoma cell proliferation and viability compared to those observed in the control cultures. A transient non-contact electric field was produced by charge-balanced biphasic stimuli through the graphene/PET film electrodes and applied to cultured neural cells. We found that weak electric field stimulation (pulse duration of 10 s) as low as 4.5 mV/mm for 32 min was particularly effective in shaping cell-to-cell interaction.

The differentiation into neurons of human neural stem cells (hNSCs) cultured on graphene has been studied by (Park et al., 2014). The results shared by the authors showed not only an improved differentiation but also an enhanced cell adhesion and neurites formation compared to control conditions. A series of voltage pulses (usually, 1 ≈ 10 of 500 mV monophasic/cathodic voltage pulses with 1 ≈ 100 ms duration in a second) were applied to the differentiated cells via the graphene electrodes.

(Li et al., 2013) designed a three-dimensional (3D) graphene foam scaffold for neural stem cells (NSC). This scaffold allowed the formation of a three-dimensional neural network, resulting in an excellent substrate for cell adhesion and proliferation by up-regulating Ki-67 protein expression. To test whether such a scaffold could be used as a neural stimulation electrode, its electrochemical properties were investigated by cyclic voltammetry. The results showed that electrical stimulation via a capacitive charge injection was enhanced (due to the larger specific surface area of the 3D scaffold) compared to the use of conventional graphene film electrode.

(Dmitry Kireev et al., 2016) prepared a graphene microelectrode array (GMEA) with 20 μm diameter on a flexible polyimide substrate. Electrical Impedance Spectroscopy using graphene as working electrode and Ag/AgCl pellet as reference electrodes in PBS solution was studied. PBS was used as electrolyte to mimic physiological condition *in vivo*. A 10 mV alternating current (AC) potential was applied and a frequency range between 1 Hz and 1MHz was scanned in order to perform extracellular recordings by measuring electrical activities from acute heart tissue and cardiac muscle cells (cardiomyocyte-like cells, HL-1). The impedance of GMEA measured at 1kHz was around $1 \pm 0.5 \times 10^5 \Omega$. The results showed good signal-to-noise ratios for both heart tissue and HL-1 cells. (Gomes et al., 2019) also fabricated a GMEA (composed of graphene microelectrodes with TiN tracks and contact pads) and reported a mean value of charge injection capacity of 0.7 mC/cm², which they claimed to be a satisfactory value and higher than the amplitudes obtained for MEAs reported in the literature. To determine if the GMEA worked properly, the authors used Electrical Impedance Spectroscopy and applied a sinusoidal excitation between 10 and 50 mV of unit frequency (<1 to 105 Hz). The produced GMEA exhibited an average impedance at 1 kHz of 5.2 kΩ. (Gomes et al., 2019) compared their results with previous studies for graphene electrodes. For instance, they cited that the 0.31 mm² electrodes prepared by (Körbitzer et al., 2019) with pure gold, graphene on gold and graphene/SiO₂, found a CIC of 0.03, 0.2 and 0.8 mC/cm², respectively. Moreover, at frequencies between 1 Hz and 1 MHz, the

lowest impedance values found were 7 k Ω , 4.4 k Ω , and 10 k Ω , for gold, graphene on gold, graphene/SiO₂, respectively.

(Du et al., 2015) reported the impedance of MEAs with graphene and with gold electrodes (20 μ m diameter) tested at frequencies between 0.1 and 100 kHz, showing higher impedance values than the ones observed by (Gomes et al., 2019) and (Körbitzer et al., 2019): 170 k Ω for the graphene electrode and 186 k Ω for the gold electrode.

In a different work, (Koerbitzer et al., 2016) prepared 3 different MEAs with an electrode size of about 700 μ m². Gold, graphene on a thin gold layer, and plain graphene were fabricated on borosilicate glass substrates. Impedance studies at 1 kHz revealed a value of 2.3 M Ω and 0.88 M Ω for plain graphene and graphene on gold, respectively. Neural cell culture was performed using cryo-conserved embryonic cortical rat neurons. Neuronal recordings showed enough signal-to-noise ratio for both electrodes and a stable impedance. Stimulation measurements yielded a CIC of 0.15 mC/cm² using biphasic pulses of 1 ms and 1 μ A for transparent graphene electrodes. (Koerbitzer et al., 2016), cited other authors, namely (Park et al., 2014), (Kuzum et al., 2014), and (Dmitry Kireev et al., 2016), who also studied different size graphene electrodes (from 310000 to 314 μ m²), on different substrates (polimide, Parylene-C, quartz glass and borosilicate glass) and then with different impedances.

5.6. Hybrid electrodes

The addition of carbon-based allotropes to conductive polymers results in electrodes with higher charge storage capacity (CSC) and lower impedance. In stimulation electrodes, a low impedance and decreased activation threshold have been achieved by several groups who have prepared hybrid electrodes.

5.6.1. PEDOT–CNT

To overcome the problems related to spatial resolution and signal-to-noise ratio, (Gerwig et al., 2012) developed a PEDOT–CNT composite coating that combined the ionic and electronic conductivity of poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT), a conductive polymer, with the high mechanical stability of carbon nanotubes (CNT). This combination, employed as a coating layer on conventional MEAs, resulted in reduced impedance (<16 k Ω @ 1 kHz), and thus in improved performances not only when compared with TiN (~50 k Ω) or Au (~330 k Ω) electrodes, but also compared to pure PEDOT electrodes (20 k Ω). The interpretation of this phenomenon can most likely be found in the conductivity of the meshwork of CNT, which enhances the electrical conductivity of the whole composite. Furthermore, PEDOT–CNT electrodes demonstrated excellent biocompatibility, allowing for the adhesion of primary chicken cardiomyocytes and the development of a two-dimensional syncytium, accompanied by good quality recording after six and ten days in vitro.

5.6.2. Polypyrrole – graphene

(Yan et al., 2016) reported the use of aligned nanofibers from polypyrrole-graphene (PPy-G) as electrodes for regeneration of optic nerve via electrical stimulation. The authors used graphene into the conductive polymers scaffold structure to make it more conductive and robust. The electrode size was 1 cm² and the scan rate was 50 mV/s. The stimulation led to 137% improvement in cell length with a significantly enhanced anti-aging effect for retinal ganglion cells. A PPy-G composite electrode was built by (Zhu et al., 2019) as an electrochemically controlled release system. The results exhibited favourable conductivity with a large capacitance and a stronger charge injection ability, which can be utilized as a drug carrier to verify the electro-responsive controlled release of fluorescein sodium. The EIS were conducted at the open circuit potential in a frequency range from 1 Hz to 100 kHz. To assess the electric responsiveness behaviour, a two-electrode electrochemical cell was designed by using Pt

electrode as the counter electrode. The best conditions were found when a constant stimulation of -1.5 V was applied.

5.6.3. Polyaniline-graphene

(Zheng et al., 2019) described a highly electroactive and biocompatible nanoelectrode made from a novel polyaniline functionalized graphene (PANI-G) composite prepared by a facile and efficient polymerization-enhanced ball-milling method. The nanoelectrode was used for the regeneration of PC12 cells (seeded with a density of $0.25 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^2$ and pre-cultured for 24h) via electrical stimulation and the results showed a 60% increase in axon length, with no adverse impact on the cell density and enhanced wound regeneration ability. The stimulation was carried out with a forward 500 mV/cm and a reverse -500 mV/cm for 1 or 3 hours each during 3, 5 and 7 days.

5.6.4. Polycaprolactone fumarate-Polypyrrole

(Moroder et al., 2011) studied the mechanical and electrical properties of polycaprolactone fumarate-polypyrrole (PCLF-PPy) scaffolds as potential conductive nerve conduits. P12 cells (PC12 is a cell line derived from a pheochromocytoma of the rat adrenal medulla) were electrically stimulated with 10 μA current for 1 h/day, either using constant direct current or direct current at 20 Hz. The surface resistivity of the scaffolds was 2 k Ω and the scaffolds were electrically stable during the application of electrical stimulation (ES). The presence of ES showed significant increases in the percentage of neurite bearing cells (67%), number of neurites per cell (52%) and neurite length (41%).

5.6.5. Polypyrrole-polydopamine

Electrically conductive polypyrrole-polydopamine (PPy-PDA) coatings were studied by (Kim et al., 2018) as high-performance biomaterials for cell stimulation in vitro and electrical signal recording in vivo. These coatings were prepared by electrochemical copolymerization with a panoply of thicknesses (and, consequently, an equal set of properties). They were applied on a gold electrode as working electrode on an electrochemical working station, that also possesses a platinum wire as a counter electrode, and a saturated calomel reference electrode (SCE). As part of the characterization of electrochemical properties, impedance spectra were collected in a range of 0.0001-10 kHz, applying an AC sinusoidal signal at 5 mV vs. SCE, in PBS solution. For electrical stimulation, 24 h after the seeding, PC12 cells were cultured for 24h and then stimulated with 100 mV for 2 h, followed by an additional 24h culture period. The electrical properties of electrodes coated with PPy-PDA were superior to electrodes coated with PPy alone. The growth and differentiation of C2C12 myoblasts and PC12 neuronal cells on PPy-PDA was enhanced compared to PPy. The PPy-PDA coated electrodes were also used on in vivo electromyography demonstrating more sensitive signals from mice tibia muscles (tibialis anterior) than bare gold or PPy-coated electrodes.

In relation of hybrid electrodes, there are other interesting works published using polypyrrole hybrids (Cui et al., 2003, 2001; Schmidt et al., 1997b; Shi et al., 2004), polyaniline hybrids (Hsiao et al., 2013; Y. Li et al., 2017; Mohammadi Amirabad et al., 2017; Petrov et al., 2016; Prabhakaran et al., 2011), as well as PEDOT-PEG (Ostrakhovitch et al., 2012),

Table 6 - Summary of systems used for electrical stimulation

System	Electrical conductivity	Biocompatibility Study	Electrical Stimulation Paradigm	Additional Notes	Ref.
<i>Metals</i>					
Platinum	N.A.	human neuroblastoma cell line SH-SY5Y	N.A.	Neural microelectrodes (with sizes between 5 and 500 μm)	(Boehler et al., 2015)
Platinum	N.A.	C2C12 muscle	pulsed of 6 V, 1 Hz and duration of 10 ms for 1 day	IDE	(Ahadian et al., 2012)
Platinum	N.A.	0.01 M PBS solution was used	120 million current controlled biphasic, cathodic-first, charge balanced pulses with a charge density of 60 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ /phase and a frequency of 500 Hz	polyimide-based thin-film platinum macro (338 and 444 μm) and micro (85 μm) electrodes for neuroprostheses, either sputter deposited or evaporated	(Pfau et al., 2019)
Platinum	N.A.	isolated porcine left cervical vagus nerve segment	Charge injection capacity of the electrode was around 75 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ and the results showed that both the most negative and positive potentials across the electrode-electrolyte interface reached -0.54 and 0.59 V, respectively, not exceeding the safe potential limits for water electrolysis.	Half-cuff electrode and containing single row of nine electrodes (0.5 x 2 mm) at 2 mm from its inner surface	(Rozman et al., 2014)
Gold	N.A.	adipose-derived stem cells (hASCs)	AC electric field of 1 V/cm, 4h for 14 days	IDE	(McCullen et al., 2010)
Gold	N.A.	cryo-conserved embryonic cortical rat neurons	CIC of 0.03. Between frequencies between 1 Hz and 1 MHz, the lowest impedance value found was 7 k Ω .	0.31 mm ² electrodes	(Koerbitzer et al., 2016)
<i>Conductive Polymers</i>					

PPy	N.A.	Dysregulation of risk genes neuregulin-1 (NRG1) and disrupted in schizophrenia 1 (DISC1) loss-of-function in pre-frontal cortical neural cells (PFC) in mice	± 0.25 mA/cm ² using a biphasic waveform of 100 μ m pulses with 20 μ m interphase open circuit potential and a 3.78 ms short circuit (250 Hz)	N.A.	(Zhang et al., 2017)
PPy	N.A.	MC3T3-E1 cells seeded at a density of 2×10^4 cells per cm ²	5 mV, 1 or 25 Hz	Planar electrodes	(Liu et al., 2018)
PPy(DBS)	N.A.	hNSCs (5×10^4 cell/cm ²)	± 0.25 mA/cm ² using a biphasic waveform of 100 μ m pulses with 20 μ m interphase open circuit potential and a 3.78 ms short circuit (250 Hz)	DBS as the anionic dopant. Grown galvanostatically on gold-coated mylar	(Stewart et al., 2015)
PPy:PSS	N.A.	PBS solution was used	AC sinusoidal signal of 5 mV amplitude and the DC potential was set to 0 V. The value of impedance was determined over a range of 10-100 000 Hz. The smaller impedance of 120 k Ω was found for 1 KHz.	Electrochemical grown on hydrogel scaffolds deposited on the surface of microfabricated neural prosthetic devices (gold electrodes)	(Kim et al., 2004)
PPy:PPS	N.A.	PBS solution was used	AC sinusoid with 5 mV of amplitude as the input signal with the DC potential set to 0 V. The value of impedance was determined at five discrete frequencies over the range of 10 to 10^5 Hz. The lowest impedance (<10 k Ω) was observed at a thickness of ~ 13 μ m.	Electrochemical grown on hydrogel scaffolds deposited on the surface of microfabricated neural prosthetic devices (gold and iridium sites with 1250 and 3900 μ m ²)	(Cui et al., 2001)
PEDOT	N.A.	ReNcellVM NSC (140 000 cells/cm ²)	100 Hz pulsed DC electrical stimulation, 1 V with 10 ms pulses	N.A.	(Pires et al., 2015)

PEDOT	N.A.	SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma-derived cells and mouse primary dissociated cortical cultures (MCC)	AC current over the frequencies of 100 – 1000 Hz. PEDOT coatings showed a decrease of the phase angle of the impedance at frequencies > 100 Hz.	PEDOT, PEDOT+live neurons and neuron-templated PEDOT coatings on Au/Pd electrodes	(Richardson-Burns et al., 2007)
PEDOT	N.A.	PBS solution was used.	5 mV sinewaves at 36 frequencies logarithmically spaced from 1 Hz to 1 MHz	PEDOT as neural interface material for microstimulation of small area (177 μm^2) iridium electrodes	(Wilks et al., 2009)
PEDOT:PSS	N.A.	PBS solution was used.	5 mA, a pulse duration of 100 μs per phase, an interphase gap (pulse pause) of 50 μs and a frequency of 1 kHz. 86.4 million bipolar current pulses per day at a current density of $2\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$	PEDOT-coated circular microelectrodes (with approximately 560 μm of diameter, $A = 0.25\text{ mm}^2$)	(Schander et al., 2016)
PEDOT:PSS	N.A.	Neural Stem Cells (NSC) seeded at 2×10^7 cells/ml (on culture dishes)	Impedance of 5-10 $\text{k}\Omega$ at 1kHz. Detection of spontaneous activity. 600 s recording with a 1 ms bin width.	Modified MEA. Square array of 8x8 ITO electrodes, each with 20 μm square and distance from the remaining with 70 μm .	(Furukawa et al., 2013)
PEDOT:Nafion	N.A.	Rat central nervous system	charge density of $0.5\text{ mC}/\text{cm}^2$ would correspond to a current amplitude of 154 μA for a stimulating pulse of 500 μs	140 μm diameter	(Carli et al., 2019)
PANI	N.A.	Human osteosarcoma (HOS) cells	800 mV and 1 kHz	N.A.	(Min et al., 2013)
PANI	N.A.	Cell viability, gene expression analysis, cytotoxicity study and calcium detection for bone marrow-derived hMSCs	Rectangular electrical pulses (7 ms, 3.6 mV/cm, 10 Hz) for 4 h followed by 4 h break for 28 days	Polymer films	(Thrivikraman et al., 2015)
PANI	N.A.	Cell proliferation of PC12 cells. Dynamic protein adsorption	Rectangular electrical pulses (100 μA , 0.8 ms) repeating every 1 s for 1, 2 and 4 h.	Nanostructured PANI on ITO glass	(Wang et al., 2015)

		analysis using the SDS-PAGE technique			
PANI	10 ⁻⁹ to 10 S/cm	hMSCs	1 mV – 2V DC field	Square-shaped films	(Thrivikraman et al., 2014)

Carbon

CNT	N.A.	Mesenchymal stem cell (MSC) with a density of 20 000 cells/cm ²	0.15V/cm for 2 ms duration at a frequency of 1Hz for more than 10 days	N.A.	(Mooney et al., 2012)
CNT	N.A.	Differentiated neural stem cells (NSCs)	5mV, 0.5 mA, 25ms intermittent	CNT synthesized by CVD and prepared it into a ropelike structure with a diameter of 1 mm and length of 1.5 cm	(Huang et al., 2012)
CNT	430 and 2140 S/m before and after heat treatment respectively	Neural stem cells (NSCs)	Series (~10-15) of 1 ms pulses spaced in 1-10 s intervals. and output currents from the film range from the order of 1-10 μ A/cm ²	CNT thin films fabricated by a layer-by-layer method with alternating layers of single walled CNT (SWCNT) and the protein laminin. Areas of the films of about 4 cm ²	(Kam et al., 2009)
CNT	N.A.	rat cortical neurons (700 cells/mm ²)	biphasic (positive-then-negative) pulses, 500 mV in amplitude, with each phase lasting 400 μ s. A stimulation session was composed of 60 pulses separated by 20 s intervals.	CNT MEAs. CNT grown by CVD on SiO ₂	(Shein et al., 2009)
CNT	N.A.	crayfish nerve cords	square pulse (amplitude of 7 V, and pulse duration of 0.1 ms) every 5 ms	CNT grown by CVD on Parylene-C film	(Lin et al., 2009)
CNT	N.A.	Chick retinas	charge-balanced bi-phasic (cathodic first) current stimulation (pulse width: 1 ms and pulse amplitude: 1–10 μ A). Each stimulation session included stimulations at the entire intensity range	CNTs were grown by CVD on polyimide and parylene C	(David-Pur et al., 2014)

			(increased by 1 μ A every 10 s) and was repeated five times.		
CNT	N.A.	Ganglion cells in rabbit retinas (seeded at a density of 2.5×10^5 cells/ml onto uncoated P35 culture dishes)	N.A.	CNT MEAs. CNTs deposited by CVD on platinum	(Gabriel et al., 2013)
Graphene	N.A.	human neural stem cells (hNSCs) for brain repair and neural regeneration	$1 \approx 10$ of 500 mV monophasic/cathodic voltage pulses with $1 \approx 100$ ms duration in a second	Graphene grown by CVD and then transferred to glass slides and coated with laminin	(Park et al., 2014)
Graphene	N.A.	Neural stem cell (seeded with a density of 5×10^4 cells/mL)	monophasic cathodic pulses were applied, and the stimulation threshold was 20–30 mA	3D graphene foam synthesized by CVD method with Ni foam as template	(Li et al., 2013)
Graphene	N.A.	Extracellular recordings by measuring electrical activities from acute heart tissue and cardiac muscle cells (cardiomyocyte-like cells, HL-1)	The impedance of GMEA measured at 1kHz was around $1 \pm 0.5 \times 10^5 \Omega$	Graphene microelectrode array (GMEA) with 20 μ m diameter on a flexible polyimide substrate	(Dmitry Kireev et al., 2016)
Graphene	N.A.	dorsal root ganglion neuron of Wistar rats	Sinusoidal excitation between 10 and 50 mV of unit frequency (<1 to 105 Hz). The produced GMEA exhibited an average impedance at 1 kHz of 5.2 k Ω .	0.31 mm ² electrodes. GMEA with TiN tracks and contact pads.	(Gomes et al., 2019)
Graphene	N.A.	cryo-conserved embryonic cortical rat neurons	CIC of 0.2 mC/cm ² . Between 1 Hz and 1 MHz, the lowest impedance value found was 4.4 k Ω .	0.31 mm ² electrodes. GMEA with graphene on gold	(Koerbitzer et al., 2016)
Graphene	N.A.	cryo-conserved embryonic cortical rat neurons	CIC of 0.8 mC/cm ² . Between 1 Hz and 1 MHz, the lowest impedance value found was 10 k Ω .	0.31 mm ² electrodes. GMEA with graphene/SiO ₂	(Koerbitzer et al., 2016)

Graphene	N.A.	rat cortical neuron	Impedance tested at frequencies between 0.1 and 100 kHz was 170 k Ω	20 μ m diameter electrodes. GMEA with graphene on gold	(Du et al., 2015)
Graphene	N.A.	Neural cell culture was performed using cryo-conserved embryonic cortical rat neurons	Impedance studies at 1 kHz revealed a value of 0.88 M Ω .	Graphene on a thin gold layer fabricated on borosilicate glass substrate. Electrode size 700 μ m ² .	(Körbitzer et al., 2019)
Graphene	N.A.	Neural cell culture was performed using cryo-conserved embryonic cortical rat neurons	CIC of 0.15 mC/cm ² using biphasic pulses of 1 ms and 1 μ A for transparent graphene electrodes. Impedance studies at 1 kHz revealed a value of 2.3 M Ω .	Graphene on a thin gold layer fabricated on borosilicate glass substrate. Electrode size 700 μ m ² .	(Körbitzer et al., 2019)
Graphene	N.A.	SHSY5Y human neuroblastoma cells (3x10 ⁵ cells in a 30 mm culture dish)	A transient non-contact electric field was produced by charge-balanced biphasic stimuli. Weak electric field stimulation (pulse duration of 10 s) as low as 4.5 mV/mm for 32 min was particularly effective in shaping cell-to-cell interaction	Graphene grown by CVD and transferred to a PET film	(Heo et al., 2011)

Hybrids

PPy-G	N.A.	Regeneration of optic nerve via electrical stimulation of retinal ganglion cells	scan rate was 50 mV/s	1 cm ² aligned nanofibers	(Yan et al., 2016)
PPy-G	N.A.	Electro-responsive controlled release of fluorescein sodium	open circuit potential in a frequency range from 1 Hz to 100 kHz. -1.5V	N.A.	(Zhu et al., 2019)
PPy-PDA	N.A.	Growth and differentiation of C2C12 myoblasts and PC12 neuronal cells	Impedance spectra were collected in a range of 0.0001-10 kHz, applying an AC sinusoidal signal at 5 mV.	Coatings applied on a gold electrode	(Kim et al., 2018)

PPy-PLGA	N.A.	PC12 cells and primary chicken sciatic nerve explants	Steady Potential of 100 mV for 2h.	Thin films grown on PLGA	(Schmidt et al., 1997b)
PPy-PDLLA	Surface resistivity 1000 Ω /square (3% PPy)	Fibroblasts	100 mV DC applied voltage for 1000 h	Composite membrane (3.0 x 2.5 x 0.03) cm ³ in size	(Shi et al., 2004)
PPy-biomolecules blend	N.A.	Rat glacial and human neuroblastoma cells	AC sinusoid with 5 mV of amplitude as the input signal with the DC potential set to 0 V. The value of impedance was determined at five discrete frequencies over the range of 10 to 10 ⁵ Hz.	PPy-biomolecules grown galvanostatically on gold sites (1250 and 3900 μ m ²). The biomolecules used were silk-like polymer having fibronectin fragments and nonapeptide (CDPGYIGSR)	(Cui et al., 2003, 2001)
PPy-neurotrophins (NT-3 and BDNF)	N.A.	Cochlear neural explant	Biphasic \pm 1 mA current pulses with 100 μ s pulse width, 20 μ s open-circuit interphase gap and 3.78 ms short-circuit phase between pulses at 250 Hz	The neurotrophin-doped PPy were galvanostatically deposited onto a 1cm ² Au-Mylar electrodes	(Thompson et al., 2010)
PEDOT-CNT	N.A.	primary chicken embryonic cardiomyocytes	iphasic anodic first voltage pulses with a frequency of 1 kHz and amplitudes of 200, 500, and 700 mV	MEA with 59 electrodes (30 μ m diameter)	(Gerwig et al., 2012)
PANI-G	N.A.	Regeneration of PC12 cells (seeded with a density of 0.25x10 ³ /mm ² and pre-cultured for 24h)	500 mV/cm and a reverse -500 mV/cm for 1 or 3 hours each during 3, 5 and 7 days	nanoelectrode	(Zheng et al., 2019)
PANI-PLLA	3.0x10 ⁻⁹ S/cm	Adhesion and proliferation of rat nerve stem cells (C17.2)	100 mV/mm for 60 minutes	Electrospun nanofibers	(Prabhakaran et al., 2011)
PANI-PLGA	N.A.	Cell viability and immunofluorescence	Electrical pulses of 1.25 Hz and 5 V/cm	Electrospun nanofibers	(Hsiao et al., 2013)

		study using Rat neonatal cardiomyocytes			
PANI-HEC	10 S/cm	Cell viability and actin fluorescent imaging of L929 mouse fibroblasts	2.5 V/cm and 2 mA for 24 h	nanocomposite	(Petrov et al., 2016)
PANI-coated PCL	6.7×10^{-3} S/cm	Cell viability of HUVECs	200, 300, and 400 mV/cm, 30 min/day, for 4 days	Fibber scaffold	(Y. Li et al., 2017)
PANI-PES	N.A.	Cell viability, RT-PCR study, karyotyping study and immunofluorescence staining of CVD-iPSCs	Electrical pulses (1 Hz for 2 ms and 50 mV/cm) for 1 h/day for 15 days	nanofibers	(Mohammadi Amirabad et al., 2017)
PCLF-PPy	surface resistivity of the scaffolds was 2 k Ω	P12 Cells	10 μ A current for 1 h/day, either using constant direct current or direct current at 20 Hz	Scaffolds as potential conductive nerve conduits	(Moroder et al., 2011)
PEDOT-PEG	$>10^{-4}$ S/cm ²	NSCs and P19 pluripotent embryonal carcinoma cells (P19 EC)	N.A.	Conductive films	(Ostrakhovitch et al., 2012)

6. FINAL REMARKS

This deliverable report presented a survey on nervous tissues stimulation techniques. The major focus was on electrical stimulation with direct coupling, since this will be the targeted approach for the systems under development in project NeuroStimSpinal. The survey presented relevant background information regarding the impedance characteristics of nervous tissues and electrochemical cells. Both present great relevance for the work under development, as they allow to take informed decisions on circuit design. Considering the stimulation system, the reported focused on the approaches referenced in the literature and derived a set of characteristics for in-vitro and in-vivo system development.

7. REFERENCES

- Adhikari, S., Sah, M., Kim, H., Chua, L.O., 2013. Three Fingerprints of Memristor. *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. Regul. Pap.*
- Ahadian, S., Ramón-Azcón, J., Ostrovidov, S., Camci-Unal, G., Hosseini, V., Kaji, H., Ino, K., Shiku, H., Khademhosseini, A., Matsue, T., 2012. Interdigitated array of Pt electrodes for electrical stimulation and engineering of aligned muscle tissue. *Lab. Chip* 12, 3491. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c2lc40479f>
- Aregueta-Robles, U.A., Woolley, A.J., Poole-Warren, L.A., Lovell, N.H., Green, R.A., 2014. Organic electrode coatings for next-generation neural interfaces. *Front. Neuroengineering* 7, 15. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fneng.2014.00015>
- Aryan, N.P., Kaim, H., Rothermel, A., 2015. Electrode Materials: State-of-the-Art and Experiments. pp. 45–64. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-10052-4_6
- Au, H.T.H., Cheng, I., Chowdhury, M.F., Radisic, M., 2007. Interactive effects of surface topography and pulsatile electrical field stimulation on orientation and elongation of fibroblasts and cardiomyocytes. *Biomaterials* 28, 4277–4293. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2007.06.001>
- Balint, R., Cassidy, N.J., Cartmell, S.H., 2013. Electrical Stimulation: A Novel Tool for Tissue Engineering. *Tissue Eng. Part B Rev.* 19, 48–57. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ten.teb.2012.0183>
- Bard, A.J., Faulkner, L.R., 2001. *Electrochemical methods: fundamentals and applications*, 2nd ed. ed. Wiley, New York.
- Bodamyali, T., Bhatt, B., Hughes, F.J., Winrow, V.R., Kanczler, J.M., Simon, B., Abbott, J., Blake, D.R., Stevens, C.R., 1998. Pulsed Electromagnetic Fields Simultaneously Induce Osteogenesis and Upregulate Transcription of Bone Morphogenetic Proteins 2 and 4 in Rat Osteoblasts in Vitro. *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.* 250, 458–461. <https://doi.org/10.1006/bbrc.1998.9243>
- Boehler, C., Kleber, C., Martini, N., Xie, Y., Dryg, I., Stieglitz, T., Hofmann, U.G., Asplund, M., 2017. Actively controlled release of Dexamethasone from neural microelectrodes in a chronic in vivo study. *Biomaterials* 129, 176–187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2017.03.019>
- Boehler, C., Stieglitz, T., Asplund, M., 2015. Nanostructured platinum grass enables superior impedance reduction for neural microelectrodes. *Biomaterials* 67, 346–353. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BIOMATERIALS.2015.07.036>
- Bozkurt, A., Lal, A., 2011. Low-cost flexible printed circuit technology based microelectrode array for extracellular stimulation of the invertebrate locomotory system. *Sens. Actuators Phys.* 169, 89–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sna.2011.05.015>
- Brighton, C.T., Wang, W., Seldes, R., Zhang, G., Pollack, S.R., 2001. Signal Transduction in Electrically Stimulated Bone Cells: *J. Bone Jt. Surg.-Am.* Vol. 83, 1514–1523. <https://doi.org/10.2106/00004623-200110000-00009>
- Burbli, N., Schulze, J., Schwarz, H.-C., Kranz, K., Motz, D., Vogt, C., Lenarz, T., Warnecke, A., Behrens, P., 2016. Coatings of Different Carbon Nanotubes on Platinum Electrodes for Neuronal Devices: Preparation, Cytocompatibility and Interaction with Spiral Ganglion Cells. *PLOS ONE* 11, e0158571. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0158571>
- Carli, S., Bianchi, M., Zucchini, E., Di Lauro, M., Prato, M., Murgia, M., Fadiga, L., Biscarini, F., 2019. Electrodeposited PEDOT:Nafion Composite for Neural Recording and Stimulation. *Adv. Healthc. Mater.* 8, 1900765. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adhm.201900765>

- Chua, L., 2018. Five non-volatile memristor enigmas solved. *Appl. Phys. A* 124, 563. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00339-018-1971-0>
- Chua, L., 2015. Everything You Wish to Know About Memristors But Are Afraid to Ask. *Radioengineering* 24, 319–368. <https://doi.org/10.13164/re.2015.0319>
- Chua, L., 2014. If it's pinched it's a memristor. *Semicond. Sci. Technol.* 29, 104001. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0268-1242/29/10/104001>
- Chua, L., 1971. Memristor-The missing circuit element. *IEEE Trans. Circuit Theory* 18, 507–519. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCT.1971.1083337>
- Chua, L., Sbitnev, V., Kim, H., 2012a. HODGKIN–HUXLEY AXON IS MADE OF MEMRISTORS. *Int. J. Bifurc. Chaos* 22, 1230011. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S021812741230011X>
- Chua, L., Sbitnev, V., Kim, H., 2012b. NEURONS ARE POISED NEAR THE EDGE OF CHAOS. *Int. J. Bifurc. Chaos* 22, 1250098. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0218127412500988>
- Chua, L.O., Kang, S.M., 1976. Memristive Devices and Systems. *Proc. IEEE* 64, 209–223. <https://doi.org/10.1109/PROC.1976.10092>
- Chung, T.-W., Huang, C.-N., Chen, P.-C., Noda, T., Tokuda, T., Ohta, J., 2018. Fabrication of Iridium Oxide/Platinum Composite Film on Titanium Substrate for High-Performance Neurostimulation Electrodes. *Coatings* 8, 420. <https://doi.org/10.3390/coatings8120420>
- Cisnal, A., Fraile, J.-C., Pérez-Turiel, J., Muñoz-Martinez, V., Müller, C., R. Ihmig, F., 2018. A Measurement Setup and Automated Calculation Method to Determine the Charge Injection Capacity of Implantable Microelectrodes. *Sensors* 18, 4152. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s18124152>
- Cong, P., 2016. Neural Interfaces for Implantable Medical Devices: Circuit Design Considerations for Sensing, Stimulation, and Safety. *IEEE Solid-State Circuits Mag.* 8, 48–56. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MSSC.2016.2573918>
- Cui, X., Hetke, J.F., Wiler, J.A., Anderson, D.J., Martin, D.C., 2001. Electrochemical deposition and characterization of conducting polymer polypyrrole/PSS on multichannel neural probes. *Sens. Actuators Phys.* 93, 8–18. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-4247\(01\)00637-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-4247(01)00637-9)
- Cui, X., Wiler, J., Dzaman, M., Altschuler, R.A., Martin, D.C., 2003. In vivo studies of polypyrrole/peptide coated neural probes. *Biomaterials* 24, 777–87. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0142-9612\(02\)00415-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0142-9612(02)00415-5)
- Dagdeviren, C., Ramadi, K.B., Joe, P., Spencer, K., Schwerdt, H.N., Shimazu, H., Delcasso, S., Amemori, K., Nunez-Lopez, C., Graybiel, A.M., Cima, M.J., Langer, R., 2018. Miniaturized neural system for chronic, local intracerebral drug delivery. *Sci. Transl. Med.* 10, ean2742. <https://doi.org/10.1126/scitranslmed.aan2742>
- David-Pur, M., Bareket-Keren, L., Beit-Yaakov, G., Raz-Prag, D., Hanein, Y., 2014. All-carbon-nanotube flexible multi-electrode array for neuronal recording and stimulation. *Biomed. Microdevices* 16, 43–53. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10544-013-9804-6>
- Du, X., Wu, L., Cheng, J., Huang, S., Cai, Q., Jin, Q., Zhao, J., 2015. Graphene microelectrode arrays for neural activity detection. *J. Biol. Phys.* 41, 339–47. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10867-015-9382-3>
- Fisher, L.E., Tyler, D.J., Anderson, J.S., Triolo, R.J., 2009. Chronic stability and selectivity of four-contact spiral nerve-cuff electrodes in stimulating the human femoral nerve. *J. Neural Eng.* 6, 046010. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1741-2560/6/4/046010>
- Furukawa, Y., Shimada, A., Kato, K., Iwata, H., Torimitsu, K., 2013. Monitoring neural stem cell differentiation using PEDOT–PSS based MEA. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta BBA - Gen. Subj.* 1830, 4329–4333. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbagen.2013.01.022>

- Gabriel, G., Illa, X., Guimera, A., Rebollo, B., Hernandez-Ferrer, J., Martin-Fernandez, I., Teresa, M., Godignon, P., V., M., Vill, R., 2013. Carbon Nanotubes as Suitable Interface for Improving Neural Recordings, in: *Physical and Chemical Properties of Carbon Nanotubes*. InTech. <https://doi.org/10.5772/52174>
- Gerwig, R., Fuchsberger, K., Schroepel, B., Link, G.S., Heusel, G., Kraushaar, U., Schuhmann, W., Stett, A., Stelzle, M., 2012. PEDOT–CNT Composite Microelectrodes for Recording and Electrostimulation Applications: Fabrication, Morphology, and Electrical Properties. *Front. Neuroengineering* 5, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fneng.2012.00008>
- Ghassemlooy, Z., Alves, L.N., Zvánovec, S., Khalighi, M.-A. (Eds.), 2017. *Visible Light Communications: Theory and Applications*, 1st ed. CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781315367330>
- Gomes, V.P., Pascon, A.M., Panepucci, R.R., Swart, J.W., 2019. Maskless production of neural-recording graphene microelectrode arrays. *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. B* 37, 022202. <https://doi.org/10.1116/1.5048216>
- Gulrez, S.K.H., Al-Assaf, S., Phillips, G.O., 2011. Hydrogels: Methods of Preparation, Characterisation and Applications, in: Carpi, A. (Ed.), *Progress in Molecular and Environmental Bioengineering - From Analysis and Modeling to Technology Applications*. InTech. <https://doi.org/10.5772/24553>
- Han, M., McCreery, D.B., 2008. A new chronic neural probe with electroplated iridium oxide microelectrodes, in: *2008 30th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society*. Presented at the 2008 30th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society, IEEE, Vancouver, BC, pp. 4220–4221. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IEMBS.2008.4650140>
- Harris, A.R., Newbold, C., Carter, P., Cowan, R., Wallace, G.G., 2018. Measuring the effective area and charge density of platinum electrodes for bionic devices. *J. Neural Eng.* 15, 046015. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1741-2552/aaba8b>
- Hartig, M., Joos, U., Wiesmann, H.-P., 2000. Capacitively coupled electric fields accelerate proliferation of osteoblast-like primary cells and increase bone extracellular matrix formation in vitro. *Eur. Biophys. J.* 29, 499–506. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s002490000100>
- Heo, C., Yoo, J., Lee, S., Jo, A., Jung, S., Yoo, H., Lee, Y.H., Suh, M., 2011. The control of neural cell-to-cell interactions through non-contact electrical field stimulation using graphene electrodes. *Biomaterials* 32, 19–27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BIOMATERIALS.2010.08.095>
- Hodgkin, A.L., Huxley, A.F., 1952. A quantitative description of membrane current and its application to conduction and excitation in nerve. *J. Physiol.* 117, 500–544.
- Hsiao, C.-W., Bai, M.-Y., Chang, Y., Chung, M.-F., Lee, T.-Y., Wu, C.-T., Maiti, B., Liao, Z.-X., Li, R.-K., Sung, H.-W., 2013. Electrical coupling of isolated cardiomyocyte clusters grown on aligned conductive nanofibrous meshes for their synchronized beating. *Biomaterials* 34, 1063–1072. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2012.10.065>
- Huang, Y.-J., Wu, H.-C., Tai, N.-H., Wang, T.-W., 2012. Carbon Nanotube Rope with Electrical Stimulation Promotes the Differentiation and Maturity of Neural Stem Cells. *Small* 8, 2869–2877. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smll.201200715>
- Jingkuang Chen, Wise, K.D., Hetke, J.F., Bledsoe, S.C., 1997. A multichannel neural probe for selective chemical delivery at the cellular level. *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* 44, 760–769. <https://doi.org/10.1109/10.605435>
- Kam, N.W.S., Jan, E., Kotov, N.A., 2009. Electrical Stimulation of Neural Stem Cells Mediated by Humanized Carbon Nanotube Composite Made with Extracellular Matrix Protein. *Nano Lett.* 9, 273–278. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl802859a>

- Kim, D.-H., Abidian, M., Martin, D.C., 2004. Conducting polymers grown in hydrogel scaffolds coated on neural prosthetic devices. *J. Biomed. Mater. Res.* 71A, 577–585. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbm.a.30124>
- Kim, E.G.R., Tu, H., Luo, H., Liu, B., Bao, S., Zhang, J., Xu, Y., 2015. 3D silicon neural probe with integrated optical fibers for optogenetic modulation. *Lab. Chip* 15, 2939–2949. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C4LC01472C>
- Kim, I.S., Song, J.K., Song, Y.M., Cho, T.H., Lee, T.H., Lim, S.S., Kim, S.J., Hwang, S.J., 2009. Novel Effect of Biphasic Electric Current on *In Vitro* Osteogenesis and Cytokine Production in Human Mesenchymal Stromal Cells. *Tissue Eng. Part A* 15, 2411–2422. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ten.tea.2008.0554>
- Kim, I.S., Song, J.K., Song, Y.M., Lee, T.H., Cho, T.H., Lim, S.S., Pan, H., Kim, S.J., Hwang, S.J., 2008. Novel action of biphasic electric current in vitro osteogenesis of human bone marrow mesenchymal stromal cells coupled with VEGF production. *Bone* 43.
- Kim, I.S., Song, J.K., Zhang, Y.L., Lee, T.H., Cho, T.H., Song, Y.M., Kim, D.K., Kim, S.J., Hwang, S.J., 2006. Biphasic electric current stimulates proliferation and induces VEGF production in osteoblasts. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta BBA - Mol. Cell Res.* 1763, 907–916. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbamcr.2006.06.007>
- Kim, M.K., Jeon, H., Lee, H.J., Je, M., 2019. Plugging Electronics Into Minds: Recent Trends and Advances in Neural Interface Microsystems. *IEEE Solid-State Circuits Mag.* 11, 29–42. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MSSC.2019.2939337>
- Kim, S., Jang, L.K., Jang, M., Lee, S., Hardy, J.G., Lee, J.Y., 2018. Electrically Conductive Polydopamine–Polypyrrole as High Performance Biomaterials for Cell Stimulation in Vitro and Electrical Signal Recording in Vivo. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 10, 33032–33042. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.8b11546>
- Kim, T. -i., McCall, J.G., Jung, Y.H., Huang, X., Siuda, E.R., Li, Y., Song, J., Song, Y.M., Pao, H.A., Kim, R.-H., Lu, C., Lee, S.D., Song, I.-S., Shin, G., Al-Hasani, R., Kim, S., Tan, M.P., Huang, Y., Omenetto, F.G., Rogers, J.A., Bruchas, M.R., 2013. Injectable, Cellular-Scale Optoelectronics with Applications for Wireless Optogenetics. *Science* 340, 211–216. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1232437>
- Kim, Y., Romero-Ortega, M.I., 2012. Material considerations for peripheral nerve interfacing. *MRS Bull.* 37, 573–580. <https://doi.org/10.1557/mrs.2012.99>
- Kireev, D., Sarik, D., Wu, T., Xie, X., Wolfrum, B., Offenhäusser, A., 2016. High throughput transfer technique: Save your graphene. *Carbon* 107, 319–324. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CARBON.2016.05.058>
- Kireev, Dmitry, Seyock, S., Ernst, M., Maybeck, V., Wolfrum, B., Offenhäusser, A., 2016. Versatile Flexible Graphene Multielectrode Arrays. *Biosensors* 7. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios7010001>
- Koerbitzer, B., Krauss, P., Nick, C., Yadav, S., Schneider, J.J., Thielemann, C., 2016. Graphene electrodes for stimulation of neuronal cells. *2D Mater.* 3, 024004. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2053-1583/3/2/024004>
- Körbitzer, B., Krauß, P., Belle, S., Schneider, J.J., Thielemann, C., 2019. Electrochemical Characterization of Graphene Microelectrodes for Biological Applications. *ChemNanoMat* 5, 427–435. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cnma.201800652>
- Kuzum, D., Takano, H., Shim, E., Reed, J.C., Juul, H., Richardson, A.G., de Vries, J., Bink, H., Dichter, M.A., Lucas, T.H., Coulter, D.A., Cubukcu, E., Litt, B., 2014. Transparent and flexible low noise graphene electrodes for simultaneous electrophysiology and neuroimaging. *Nat. Commun.* 5, 5259. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms6259>

- Li, N., Zhang, Q., Gao, S., Song, Q., Huang, R., Wang, L., Liu, L., Dai, J., Tang, M., Cheng, G., 2013. Three-dimensional graphene foam as a biocompatible and conductive scaffold for neural stem cells. *Sci. Rep.* 3, 1604. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep01604>
- Li, X., Zhong, S., Morizio, J., 2017. 16-Channel biphasic current-mode programmable charge balanced neural stimulation. *Biomed. Eng. OnLine* 16, 104. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12938-017-0385-0>
- Li, Y., Li, X., Zhao, R., Wang, Chuying, Qiu, F., Sun, B., Ji, H., Qiu, J., Wang, Ce, 2017. Enhanced adhesion and proliferation of human umbilical vein endothelial cells on conductive PANI-PCL fiber scaffold by electrical stimulation. *Mater. Sci. Eng. C* 72, 106–112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MSEC.2016.11.052>
- Lim, J.-H., McCullen, S.D., Piedrahita, J.A., Lobo, E.G., Olby, N.J., 2013. Alternating Current Electric Fields of Varying Frequencies: Effects on Proliferation and Differentiation of Porcine Neural Progenitor Cells. *Cell. Reprogramming* 15, 405–412. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cell.2013.0001>
- Lin, C.-M., Lee, Y.-T., Yeh, S.-R., Fang, W., 2009. Flexible carbon nanotubes electrode for neural recording. *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 24, 2791–2797. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BIOS.2009.02.005>
- Liu, Z., Dong, L., Cheng, K., Luo, Z., Weng, W., 2018. Charge injection based electrical stimulation on polypyrrole planar electrodes to regulate cellular osteogenic differentiation. *RSC Adv.* 8, 18470–18479. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8RA02601G>
- Liu, Z., Dong, L., Wang, L., Wang, X., Cheng, K., Luo, Z., Weng, W., 2017. Mediation of cellular osteogenic differentiation through daily stimulation time based on polypyrrole planar electrodes. *Sci. Rep.* 7, 17926. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-17120-8>
- Lohmann, C.H., Schwartz, Z., Liu, Y., Li, Z., Simon, B.J., Sylvia, V.L., Dean, D.D., Bonewald, L.F., Donahue, H.J., Boyan, B.D., 2003. Pulsed electromagnetic fields affect phenotype and connexin 43 protein expression in MLO-Y4 osteocyte-like cells and ROS 17/2.8 osteoblast-like cells. *J. Orthop. Res.* 21, 326–334. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0736-0266\(02\)00137-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0736-0266(02)00137-7)
- Lu, Y., Lyu, H., Richardson, A.G., Lucas, T.H., Kuzum, D., 2016. Flexible Neural Electrode Array Based-on Porous Graphene for Cortical Microstimulation and Sensing. *Sci. Rep.* 6, 33526. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep33526>
- Martins, P.A., 2019. Instrumentação para biossensor eletroquímico utilizando voltametria cíclica e espectroscopia de impedância eletroquímica. Universidade de Aveiro, Aveiro.
- McCullen, S.D., McQuilling, J.P., Grossfeld, R.M., Lubischer, J.L., Clarke, L.I., Lobo, E.G., 2010. Application of low-frequency alternating current electric fields via interdigitated electrodes: effects on cellular viability, cytoplasmic calcium, and osteogenic differentiation of human adipose-derived stem cells. *Tissue Eng. Part C Methods* 16, 1377–86. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ten.TEC.2009.0751>
- McLeod, K.J., Donahue, H.J., Levin, P.E., Fontaine, M.-A., Rubin, C.T., 1993. Electric fields modulate bone cell function in a density-dependent manner. *J. Bone Miner. Res.* 8, 977–984. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbmr.5650080811>
- Min, Y., Yang, Y., Poojari, Y., Liu, Y., Wu, J.-C., Hansford, D.J., Epstein, A.J., 2013. Sulfonated Polyaniline-Based Organic Electrodes for Controlled Electrical Stimulation of Human Osteosarcoma Cells. *Biomacromolecules* 14, 1727–1731. <https://doi.org/10.1021/bm301221t>
- Mohammadi Amirabad, L., Massumi, M., Shamsara, M., Shabani, I., Amari, A., Mossahebi Mohammadi, M., Hosseinzadeh, S., Vakilian, S., Steinbach, S.K., Khorramzadeh, M.R., Soleimani, M., Barzin, J., 2017. Enhanced Cardiac Differentiation of Human Cardiovascular Disease Patient-Specific Induced Pluripotent Stem Cells by Applying

- Unidirectional Electrical Pulses Using Aligned Electroactive Nanofibrous Scaffolds. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 9, 6849–6864. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.6b15271>
- Molen, M.A., Donahue, H.J., Rubin, C.T., McLeod, K.J., 2000. Osteoblastic networks with deficient coupling: differential effects of magnetic and electric field exposure. *Bone* 27, 227–231. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S8756-3282\(00\)00315-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S8756-3282(00)00315-X)
- Monaco, A.M., Giugliano, M., 2014. Carbon-based smart nanomaterials in biomedicine and neuroengineering. *Beilstein J. Nanotechnol.* 5, 1849–1863. <https://doi.org/10.3762/BJNANO.5.196>
- Mooney, E., Mackle, J.N., Blond, D.J.-P., O’Cearbhaill, E., Shaw, G., Blau, W.J., Barry, F.P., Barron, V., Murphy, J.M., 2012. The electrical stimulation of carbon nanotubes to provide a cardiomimetic cue to MSCs. *Biomaterials* 33, 6132–6139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2012.05.032>
- Moroder, P., Runge, M.B., Wang, H., Ruesink, T., Lu, L., Spinner, R.J., Windebank, A.J., Yaszemski, M.J., 2011. Material properties and electrical stimulation regimens of polycaprolactone fumarate-polypyrrole scaffolds as potential conductive nerve conduits. *Acta Biomater.* 7, 944–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2010.10.013>
- Neeves, K.B., Lo, C.T., Foley, C.P., Saltzman, W.M., Olbricht, W.L., 2006. Fabrication and characterization of microfluidic probes for convection enhanced drug delivery. *J. Controlled Release* 111, 252–262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2005.11.018>
- Nimbalkar, S., Castagnola, E., Balasubramani, A., Scarpellini, A., Samejima, S., Khorasani, A., Boissenin, A., Thongpang, S., Moritz, C., Kassegne, S., 2018. Ultra-Capacitive Carbon Neural Probe Allows Simultaneous Long-Term Electrical Stimulations and High-Resolution Neurotransmitter Detection. *Sci. Rep.* 8, 6958. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-25198-x>
- Olivieri, A.C., Faber, N.K.M., Ferré, J., Boqué, R., Kalivas, J.H., Mark, H., 2006. Uncertainty estimation and figures of merit for multivariate calibration (IUPAC Technical, Report 1998). *Pure Appl Chem* 78, 633–661. <https://doi.org/10.1351/pac200678030633>
- Ostrakhovitch, E.A., Byers, J.C., O’Neil, K.D., Semenikhin, O.A., 2012. Directed differentiation of embryonic P19 cells and neural stem cells into neural lineage on conducting PEDOT–PEG and ITO glass substrates. *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.* 528, 21–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.abb.2012.08.006>
- Park, D.-W., Schendel, A.A., Mikael, S., Brodnick, S.K., Richner, T.J., Ness, J.P., Hayat, M.R., Atry, F., Frye, S.T., Pashaie, R., Thongpang, S., Ma, Z., Williams, J.C., 2014. Graphene-based carbon-layered electrode array technology for neural imaging and optogenetic applications. *Nat. Commun.* 5, 5258. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms6258>
- Park, S., Jang, Y., Kim, H.C., Chun, K., 2008. Fabrication of drug delivery system with piezoelectric micropump for neural probe. *Proc ITC-CSCC Int Tech Conf Circuits Syst. Comput. Commun.* 1149–1152.
- Petrov, P., Mokreva, P., Kostov, I., Uzunova, V., Tzoneva, R., 2016. Novel electrically conducting 2-hydroxyethylcellulose/polyaniline nanocomposite cryogels: Synthesis and application in tissue engineering. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 140, 349–355. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CARBPOL.2015.12.069>
- Pfau, J., Ganatra, D., Weltin, A., Urban, G., Kieninger, J., Stieglitz, T., 2019. Electrochemical Stability of Thin-Film Platinum as Suitable Material for Neural Stimulation Electrodes, in: 2019 41st Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC). IEEE, pp. 3762–3765. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EMBC.2019.8856621>
- Pires, F., Ferreira, Q., Rodrigues, C.A.V., Morgado, J., Ferreira, F.C., 2015. Neural stem cell differentiation by electrical stimulation using a cross-linked PEDOT substrate:

- Expanding the use of biocompatible conjugated conductive polymers for neural tissue engineering. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta BBA - Gen. Subj.* 1850, 1158–1168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbagen.2015.01.020>
- Prabhakaran, M.P., Ghasemi-Mobarakeh, L., Jin, G., Ramakrishna, S., 2011. Electrospun conducting polymer nanofibers and electrical stimulation of nerve stem cells. *J. Biosci. Bioeng.* 112, 501–507. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiosc.2011.07.010>
- Radisic, M., Park, H., Shing, H., Consi, T., Schoen, F.J., Langer, R., Freed, L.E., Vunjak-Novakovic, G., 2004. Functional assembly of engineered myocardium by electrical stimulation of cardiac myocytes cultured on scaffolds. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 101, 18129–18134. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0407817101>
- Retterer, S.T., Smith, K.L., Bjornsson, C.S., Turner, J.N., Isaacson, M.S., Shain, W., 2008. Constant pressure fluid infusion into rat neocortex from implantable microfluidic devices. *J. Neural Eng.* 5, 385–391. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1741-2560/5/4/003>
- Richardson-Burns, S.M., Hendricks, J.L., Foster, B., Povlich, L.K., Kim, D.-H., Martin, D.C., 2007. Polymerization of the conducting polymer poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT) around living neural cells. *Biomaterials* 28, 1539–1552. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2006.11.026>
- Rozman, J., Pečlin, P., Mehle, A., Šala, M., 2014. Electrochemical performance of platinum electrodes within the multi-electrode spiral nerve cuff. *Australas. Phys. Eng. Sci. Med.* 37, 525–533. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13246-014-0282-9>
- Rubehn, B., Wolff, S.B.E., Tovote, P., Schuettler, M., Luthi, A., Stieglitz, T., 2011. Polymer-based shaft microelectrodes with optical and fluidic capabilities as a tool for optogenetics, in: 2011 Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society. Presented at the 2011 33rd Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society, IEEE, Boston, MA, pp. 2969–2972. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IEMBS.2011.6090815>
- Sah, M.P., Hyongsuk Kim, Chua, L.O., 2014. Brains Are Made of Memristors. *IEEE Circuits Syst. Mag.* 14, 12–36. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCAS.2013.2296414>
- Schander, A., Tesmann, T., Stokov, S., Stemmann, H., Kreiter, A.K., Lang, W., 2016. In-vitro evaluation of the long-term stability of PEDOT:PSS coated microelectrodes for chronic recording and electrical stimulation of neurons, in: 2016 38th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC). IEEE, pp. 6174–6177. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EMBC.2016.7592138>
- Schmidt, C.E., Shastri, V.R., Vacanti, J.P., Langer, R., 1997a. Stimulation of neurite outgrowth using an electrically conducting polymer. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 94, 8948–8953. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.94.17.8948>
- Schmidt, C.E., Shastri, V.R., Vacanti, J.P., Langer, R., 1997b. Stimulation of neurite outgrowth using an electrically conducting polymer. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 94, 8948–8953. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.94.17.8948>
- Scholz, F., 2015. Voltammetric techniques of analysis: the essentials. *ChemTexts* 1, 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40828-015-0016-y>
- Schwaerzle, M., Paul, O., Ruther, P., 2017. Compact silicon-based optrode with integrated laser diode chips, SU-8 waveguides and platinum electrodes for optogenetic applications. *J. Micromechanics Microengineering* 27, 065004. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6439/aa6ad4>
- Serena, E., Figallo, E., Tandon, N., Cannizzaro, C., Gerecht, S., Elvassore, N., Vunjak-Novakovic, G., 2009. Electrical stimulation of human embryonic stem cells: Cardiac differentiation and the generation of reactive oxygen species. *Exp. Cell Res.* 315, 3611–3619. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yexcr.2009.08.015>

- Shah, S., Firlak, M., Berrow, S., Halcovitch, N., Baldock, S., Yousafzai, B., Hathout, R., Hardy, J., 2018. Electrochemically Enhanced Drug Delivery Using Polypyrrole Films. *Materials* 11, 1123. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma11071123>
- Shein, M., Greenbaum, A., Gabay, T., Sorkin, R., David-Pur, M., Ben-Jacob, E., Hanein, Y., 2009. Engineered neuronal circuits shaped and interfaced with carbon nanotube microelectrode arrays. *Biomed. Microdevices* 11, 495–501. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10544-008-9255-7>
- Shi, G., Rouabhia, M., Wang, Z., Dao, L.H., Zhang, Z., 2004. A novel electrically conductive and biodegradable composite made of polypyrrole nanoparticles and polylactide. *Biomaterials* 25, 2477–2488. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BIOMATERIALS.2003.09.032>
- Shi, G., Zhang, Z., Rouabhia, M., 2008. The regulation of cell functions electrically using biodegradable polypyrrole–polylactide conductors. *Biomaterials* 29, 3792–3798. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2008.06.010>
- Shin, H., Lee, H.J., Chae, U., Kim, H., Kim, J., Choi, N., Woo, J., Cho, Y., Lee, C.J., Yoon, E.-S., Cho, I.-J., 2015. Neural probes with multi-drug delivery capability. *Lab. Chip* 15, 3730–3737. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5LC00582E>
- Son, Y., Jenny Lee, H., Kim, J., Shin, H., Choi, N., Justin Lee, C., Yoon, E.-S., Yoon, E., Wise, K.D., Geun Kim, T., Cho, I.-J., 2015. In vivo optical modulation of neural signals using monolithically integrated two-dimensional neural probe arrays. *Sci. Rep.* 5, 15466. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep15466>
- Stewart, E., Kobayashi, N.R., Higgins, M.J., Quigley, A.F., Jamali, S., Moulton, S.E., Kapsa, R.M.I., Wallace, G.G., Crook, J.M., 2015. Electrical stimulation using conductive polymer polypyrrole promotes differentiation of human neural stem cells: a biocompatible platform for translational neural tissue engineering. *Tissue Eng. Part C Methods* 21, 385–93. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ten.TEC.2014.0338>
- Strukov, D.B., Snider, G.S., Stewart, D.R., Williams, R.S., 2008. The missing memristor found. *Nature* 453, 80–83. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature06932>
- Sun, S., Titushkin, I., Cho, M., 2006. Regulation of mesenchymal stem cell adhesion and orientation in 3D collagen scaffold by electrical stimulus. *Bioelectrochemistry* 69, 133–141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioelechem.2005.11.007>
- Thaning, E.M., Asplund, M.L.M., Nyberg, T.A., Inganäs, O.W., von Holst, H., 2010. Stability of poly(3,4-ethylene dioxythiophene) materials intended for implants. *J. Biomed. Mater. Res. B Appl. Biomater.* 93B, 407–415. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbm.b.31597>
- Thompson, B.C., Richardson, R.T., Moulton, S.E., Evans, A.J., O’Leary, S., Clark, G.M., Wallace, G.G., 2010. Conducting polymers, dual neurotrophins and pulsed electrical stimulation — Dramatic effects on neurite outgrowth. *J. Controlled Release* 141, 161–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2009.09.016>
- Thrivikraman, G., Lee, P.S., Hess, R., Haenchen, V., Basu, B., Scharnweber, D., 2015. Interplay of Substrate Conductivity, Cellular Microenvironment, and Pulsatile Electrical Stimulation toward Osteogenesis of Human Mesenchymal Stem Cells in Vitro. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 7, 23015–23028. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.5b06390>
- Thrivikraman, G., Madras, G., Basu, B., 2014. Intermittent electrical stimuli for guidance of human mesenchymal stem cell lineage commitment towards neural-like cells on electroconductive substrates. *Biomaterials* 35, 6219–6235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2014.04.018>
- Tu, Q., Pang, L., Chen, Y., Zhang, Y., Zhang, R., Lu, B., Wang, J., 2014. Effects of surface charges of graphene oxide on neuronal outgrowth and branching. *The Analyst* 139, 105–115. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C3AN01796F>

- Vafaiee, M., Vossoughi, M., Mohammadpour, R., Sasanpour, P., 2019. Gold-Plated Electrode with High Scratch Strength for Electrophysiological Recordings. *Sci. Rep.* 9, 2985. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-39138-w>
- Vitale, F., Summerson, S.R., Aazhang, B., Kemere, C., Pasquali, M., 2015. Neural Stimulation and Recording with Bidirectional, Soft Carbon Nanotube Fiber Microelectrodes. *ACS Nano* 9, 4465–4474. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.5b01060>
- Wang, L., Huang, Q., Wang, J.-Y., 2015. Nanostructured Polyaniline Coating on ITO Glass Promotes the Neurite Outgrowth of PC 12 Cells by Electrical Stimulation. *Langmuir* 31, 12315–12322. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.langmuir.5b00992>
- Weiland, J.D., Anderson, D.J., Humayun, M.S., 2002. In vitro electrical properties for iridium oxide versus titanium nitride stimulating electrodes. *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* 49, 1574–1579. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TBME.2002.805487>
- Wellman, S.M., Eles, J.R., Ludwig, K.A., Seymour, J.P., Michelson, N.J., McFadden, W.E., Vazquez, A.L., Kozai, T.D.Y., 2018. A Materials Roadmap to Functional Neural Interface Design. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 28, 1701269. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201701269>
- Wilks, S.J., Richardson-Burns, S.M., Hendricks, J.L., Martin, D.C., Otto, K.J., 2009. Poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) as a Micro-Neural Interface Material for Electrostimulation. *Front. Neuroengineering* 2, 7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/neuro.16.007.2009>
- Wu, F., Stark, E., Im, M., Cho, I.-J., Yoon, E.-S., Buzsáki, G., Wise, K.D., Yoon, E., 2013. An implantable neural probe with monolithically integrated dielectric waveguide and recording electrodes for optogenetics applications. *J. Neural Eng.* 10, 056012. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1741-2560/10/5/056012>
- Wu, F., Stark, E., Ku, P.-C., Wise, K.D., Buzsáki, G., Yoon, E., 2015. Monolithically Integrated μ LEDs on Silicon Neural Probes for High-Resolution Optogenetic Studies in Behaving Animals. *Neuron* 88, 1136–1148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2015.10.032>
- Yan, L., Zhao, B., Liu, X., Li, X., Zeng, C., Shi, H., Xu, X., Lin, T., Dai, L., Liu, Y., 2016. Aligned Nanofibers from Polypyrrole/Graphene as Electrodes for Regeneration of Optic Nerve via Electrical Stimulation. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 8, 6834–6840. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.5b12843>
- Yang, W., Broski, A., Wu, J., Fan, Q.H., Li, W., 2018. Characteristics of Transparent, PEDOT:PSS-Coated Indium-Tin-Oxide (ITO) Microelectrodes. *IEEE Trans. Nanotechnol.* 17, 701–704. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TNANO.2017.2785627>
- Zhang, Q., Esrafilzadeh, D., Crook, J.M., Kapsa, R., Stewart, E.M., Tomaskovic-Crook, E., Wallace, G.G., Huang, X.-F., 2017. Electrical Stimulation Using Conductive Polymer Polypyrrole Counters Reduced Neurite Outgrowth of Primary Prefrontal Cortical Neurons from NRG1-KO and DISC1-LI Mice. *Sci. Rep.* 7, 42525. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep42525>
- Zheng, Z., Huang, L., Yan, L., Yuan, F., Wang, L., Wang, K., Lawson, T., Lin, M., Liu, Y., 2019. Polyaniline Functionalized Graphene Nanoelectrodes for the Regeneration of PC12 Cells via Electrical Stimulation. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 20, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms20082013>
- Zhu, M., Hao, Y., Ma, X., Feng, L., Zhai, Y., Ding, Y., Cheng, G., 2019. Construction of a graphene/polypyrrole composite electrode as an electrochemically controlled release system. *RSC Adv.* 9, 12667–12674. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9RA00800D>
- Zhuang, H., Wang, W., Seldes, R.M., Tahernia, A.D., Fan, H., Brighton, C.T., 1997. Electrical Stimulation Induces the Level of TGF- β 1 mRNA in Osteoblastic Cells by a Mechanism Involving Calcium/Calmodulin Pathway. *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.* 237, 5.

